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**Long-range Energy Alternatives Planning Scenarios to Mitigate
GHG Emissions from Energy Sector
A LEAP Model Application of Egypt's Energy Sector**

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Abstract

This study aims to identify energy mix scenarios of least economic cost and global warming potential that address Egypt's growing energy demand, while transitioning away from reliance on fossil fuel towards a sustainable energy landscape. The study utilized a modelling approach, the Long-range Energy Alternatives Planning system (LEAP), to simulate Egypt's energy demand and supply from 2010 to 2050. Four alternative scenarios were analyzed. The reference scenario RS1, replicates demand change patterns between 2010 and 2022, through 2050. Reference scenario RS2 considers 5% yearly growth in energy demand from 2022 to 2050. Alongside two renewables-promotion scenarios, RE1 and RE2, wherein renewables contribute 42% and 75% of the energy mix by 2030 and 2050. Results show that greenhouse gas emissions will peak in RS1 and reach its lowest level in RE2 by 2050. Energy generation costs will be the highest in RS2 by 2050, and in RE2 between 2022 and 2030, reaching its lowermost point in RE2 by 2050. Moreover, natural gas is expected to contribute the largest share of energy generated in RS1 but the smallest share in RE2 wherein wind energy dominates energy production by 2050. Among all other scenarios, RE2 has the greatest potential to enable the achievement of net-zero emissions.

Keywords: Climate Change, Egypt, Energy Modelling, LEAP.

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Summary

In 2023, Egypt reaffirmed its dedication to the Paris Agreement by submitting its updated Nationally Determined Contributions to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. This plan outlines a fifteen-year strategy from 2015 to 2030 aimed at significantly reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The targets include a 37% reduction in emissions from the electricity sector (generation, transmission, and distribution), 65% reduction from the oil and gas sector, and 7% reduction from the transportation sector, compared to 2015 levels. However, the country's economic expansion aspirations and the expected rise in energy consumption to achieve these objectives are likely to pose challenges, particularly for the energy sector. To address these challenges, this study has been conducted to examine pathways for a seamless transition from fossil fuels to cleaner energy alternatives in Egypt while ensuring continued economic growth. The thesis is structured into four chapters. The first chapter introduces the different definitions of climate change and presents the most important theories in the field. Chapter two delves into the environmental economics theory, explaining how it can be utilized to deepen our understanding of climate change from an economic perspective, followed by a thorough review of the relevant literature on the topic. Moving forward, chapter three explores further the phenomenon of climate change within the Egyptian context, followed by an overview of the energy sector in Egypt and the significant role it plays as a major contributor to GHG emissions. Chapter four addresses the methodology, materials, and techniques used in the study, and presents research results. The study concludes by summarizing key findings and discussing their policy implications, as well as their contribution to a deeper understanding of the various energy policy options.

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

CAPMAS	Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics
CBE	Central Bank of Egypt
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
COP	Conference of the Parties
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
EEAA	Egyptian Environmental Affairs Agency
EEREI	Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy Program for the Industrial Sector
EIA	Energy Information Administration
EKC	Environmental Kuznets Curve
ENSO	El Niño-Southern Oscillation
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
ESOMs	Energy System Optimization Models
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ITA	Information Trade Administration
kWh	Kilowatt-hours
LEAP	Long-range Energy Alternatives Planning
LULUCF	Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
MARKAL/ TIMES	Market Allocation and The Integrated MARKAL-EFOM System
MEDEAS	Modelling Energy System Development under Environmental and Socioeconom Constraints
MoERE	Ministry of Electricity and Renewable Energy
MPED	Ministry of Planning and Economic Development
MtCO _{2e}	Million Tons Carbon Dioxide Equivalent
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NDCs	Nationally Determined Contributions
NEEAP	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
NOAA	US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
OSeMOSYS	Open-Source Energy Modelling Systems
PV	Photovoltaic
RE1	Renewables-promotion scenario1
RE2	Renewables-promotion scenario2
RS1	Reference Scenario1
RS2	Reference Scenario2
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
TWh	Terawatt-hours
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
WHO	World Health Organization

Introduction

Climate change is a subject of global concern that marks the shifting dynamics of the earth's climate system, characterized by new weather patterns over extended periods. Many scientists propose that human activities, primarily related to burning fossil fuels, have markedly amplified these changes, resulting in what is often called global warming, the primary factor contributing to climate change. This phenomenon has led to drastic alterations influencing not just atmospheric and oceanic temperatures, but also affecting precipitation, wind patterns, and more. The consequences of such large-scale transformations are enormous, impacting biodiversity, food and water security, and posing many existential threats to humanity (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 1990, 1992, 1994, 1995). Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are the main driver of climate change. Excess amounts of these emissions trap heat in the atmosphere causing global average temperatures to increase and the Earth's climate to warm causing extreme weather events such as heatwaves, floods, sea-level rise, and other climate-related impacts. As temperature rises, more greenhouse gases are released into the atmosphere leading to a further increase in temperature and more severe climate-related consequences, posing as such significant threats to ecosystems and inducing over time irreversible consequences to the environment, economies, and societies (Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), 2023).

The impacts of climate change are far-reaching and have the potential to affect all facets of life on our planet. Some of its most evident effects on the environment include rising global temperatures, sea-level rise, and melting of polar ice caps, which puts an immense strain on marine ecosystems and coastal infrastructure and has the ability to displace millions of people residing in littoral areas across the world. Climate change can also bring on imperative ramifications to key economic sectors such as energy, agriculture, manufacturing, and tourism. Variations in rainfall patterns can result in arable land degradation and lead to diminished agricultural productivity, food shortages, and quality of crops, putting significant pressure on food value chains and water resources of affected regions and contributes to economic disparities and instabilities (IPCC, 2021, 2022). There has been a noticeable upsurge in the frequency of occurrence, scale, and intensity of extreme weather events such as tropical storms, hurricanes, typhoons, and cyclones over the past ten years across various regions in the world, indicating a strong shift in climate patterns. Examples of catastrophic environmental incidences are quite plentiful, including the series of ongoing heatwaves and wildfires that started in 2020 in Siberia, one of the coldest and most frigid parts on planet, where rising temperatures provoked a historical drought and triggered unprecedented number of fires causing the killing of hundreds of civilians and driving severe ecological damages ((National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), 2020a; Greenpeace International, 2021; NASA, 2022b; Reuters, 2023). Devastating wildfires have recently sparked over the past few years due to the rising temperatures in multiple coastal areas of the United States, Australia, and Brazil, where pollutants affected the lives of millions of people and led to the displacement of thousands of people and the demolition of billions of animal natural habitats (NASA, 2018, 2019, 2020b, 2020c). Similar occurrences of highly destructive wildfires have erupted in various regions

of Canada in recent years, casting shadows over the skies of southwestern Europe as plumes of soot, black carbon particles of smoke, traversed the Atlantic Ocean (NASA, 2022b, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c). In this context, the Paris Agreement has emerged as a significant global treaty that provides a framework for countries to control their emissions, promote sustainable development, and improve their ability to withstand the impacts of climate change by committing to the long-term objective of upholding global temperature to a level significantly below 2 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels, with an ambitious aim to strive for 1.5 degrees Celsius (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), 2015).

One of the significant achievements of the Paris Agreement is the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), under which each participating country sets its own targets and actions to reduce emissions and adapt to the impacts of climate change. These NDCs are not legally binding but are expected to be regularly updated to gradually increase ambition over time. The Agreement works on a five-year cycle of progressively ambitious climate action where a global stocktake is mandated every five years to assess collective progress towards long-term goals (UNFCCC, 2022). However, although there have been advancements in the global adoption of renewable energy since the signing of the Paris Agreement, CO₂ emissions have predominantly risen, largely due to the insufficient NDCs and inadequate mitigation measures aimed at achieving the targets set out by the Paris Agreement (UNEP, 2022). Against this backdrop, the global state of clean energy practice is entering a critical phase, owing its attributes to the significant growth of global greenhouse gas emissions specifically from the energy sector as a primary contributor to global emissions accounting solely for 75% of global emissions, where fossil fuels including oil and natural gas, dominate energy production and emit large amounts of carbon dioxide (CO₂) when burned (International Energy Agency (IEA), 2023).

- **Statement of Research Problem**

In recent years, climate change has had a considerable impact on Egypt, demonstrated by rising temperatures and changing precipitation patterns which have led to an increase in the intensity and frequency of extreme weather events. These impacts also had substantial effects on vital aspects of the country's infrastructure and imposed many consequences on critical economic sectors, particularly the energy sector. Additionally, Egypt's increasing population and aspiring economic prospects have created a surging demand for energy, coupled with rapid urbanization and industrialization, extending to electricity usage. Demonstrating its unwavering commitment to the Paris Agreement, Egypt submitted its second updated NDCs to the UNFCCC in 2023, outlining a fifteen-year working plan from 2015 to 2030 that aims to reduce GHG emissions by 37% from the electricity sector (generation, transmission, and distribution), 65% from oil and gas sector, and 7% from the transportation sector, compared to 2015 levels. Nevertheless, with the country's ambitions for economic expansion and the anticipated surge in energy consumption necessary to achieve these objectives, despite the reported progress in the electricity sector, it is likely that some challenges may arise, for the energy sector in particular. It is important therefore that Egypt explores alternative approaches to tackle energy challenges at hand, prioritizing sustainable practices that ensure long-term energy security and mitigate the adversities of climate change.

- **Research Questions**

The study seeks to investigate the intricate relationship between energy supply scenarios, GHG emissions, and economic growth in Egypt. Understanding how different energy strategies can align with environmental goals while promoting economic development is crucial for the country's sustainable future. To achieve this, the study aims to address the following main research question; **“What energy supply scenarios with the lowest potential for GHG emissions best meet Egypt’s future energy demand?”** In addition to three sub-questions;

1. How can climate change be explained through the lens of environmental economics theory?
2. What are the drivers of climate change in Egypt, and what potential impacts do they pose?
3. How does the integration of renewable energy sources into the current energy mix influence GHG emissions trends compared to scenarios that rely on fossil fuels?

- **Research Objectives**

The primary objective of the study is to develop alternative energy supply pathways that prioritize GHG emissions reduction, ensuring compatibility with Egypt's future energy demand necessary for the country’s plans for economic expansion. In addition to this main goal, the study aims to:

1. Build a comprehensive model that analyzes Egypt's energy demand and supply over the period from 2010 to 2050.
2. Establish sustainable energy pathways that address key aspects including the achievement of the country's 2030 emissions mitigation targets as outlined in the Paris Agreement.
3. Suggest alternative energy generation scenarios that facilitate the achievement of net-zero emissions in the long term.
4. Provide data-driven insights that inform sustainable energy planning strategies, policy development, and investment decisions that support Egypt's energy transition toward a low-emission future.

- **Research Methodology**

The study employs both quantitative and qualitative approaches, alongside a modelling framework, namely the Long-range Energy Alternatives Planning system (LEAP), to simulate Egypt’s energy demand and supply from 2010 to 2050. By analyzing the data generated through this process, the study explores various energy mix possibilities, energy sources and technologies to identify pathways that effectively address Egypt’ growing energy demand while remaining committed to reducing GHG emissions, in line with the objectives outlined in the Paris Agreement. Four alternative scenarios were examined; the business-as-usual scenario (BAS) is used as the foundational framework for the model extending from the period from 2010 to 2021. The reference scenario RS1, replicates the energy demand and supply change patterns of the model’s baseline until 2050. The reference scenario RS2, models the dynamics of energy demand and supply of BAS considering a yearly increase of 5% in energy consumption and integrates nuclear energy into the energy mix. The study analyzed two more scenarios, RE1 and RE2, that aim to promote the renewables’ share in the overall energy mix to 42 and 75% by 2030 and 2050, respectively.

- **Data Sources**

The analysis used secondary data from the statistical yearbook for values of key assumption parameters such as population size, gross domestic product, and relative distribution of population across urban and rural areas for the period between 2010 and 2021 (Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics (CAPMAS), 2022). For values of input variables including energy demand, energy generation technologies and their associated capacities, measures of efficiency pertaining to certain technologies, availability, capacity credit values, information on primary energy sources, the capacity of renewable energy sources for generating energy, fossil fuel reserves, energy prices, and production costs, including initial costs of energy production technologies, the analysis utilized data from the annual reports of Ministry of Electricity and Renewable Energy (MoERE) between 2010 and 2021 (MoERE, 2010, 2011, 2012a, 2013, 2014, 2015a, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019b, 2020b, 2021b).

Load shape hourly data, for setting up yearly load shape and time slices in the LEAP system, was obtained from the National Energy Control Center for 2021 (National Energy Control Center, 2021). The study employed data pertaining to operation costs for nuclear, gas turbine, combined-cycle, and hydro power plants, from the 2020 report by the US Energy Information Administration on capital costs and performance characteristics for utility-scale power generating technologies (Energy Information Administration, 2020). Meanwhile, for operational costs of other power generation technologies such as steam, wind, PV, and CSP power plants, the analysis utilized data from Egypt's Integrated Sustainable Energy Strategy (Supreme Energy Council, 2016).

Moreover, the analysis applied average values of historical monthly interest rate data and historical exchange rate data provided by the Central Bank of Egypt in 2021 for the calculation and projection of costs and energy prices (Central Bank of Egypt, 2021a, 2021b). The study utilized data from Egypt's Integrated Sustainable Energy Strategy (ISES) and Egypt's second updated NDCs (ARE, 2023) for specifications of constraints pertaining to nuclear energy, GHG emissions, and renewables. Emission factor for fuel types were all sourced from the LEAP system database, aligning with the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change guidelines for national greenhouse gas inventories IPCC 2006-Tier 1 (IPCC, 2006).

- **Research Significance**

In the existing literature on Egypt's energy sector, there has been a noticeable gap in the development of an integrated model that combines both energy demand and supply. Previous studies have predominantly focused on either energy demand analysis or energy supply analysis in isolation, overlooking the interconnected nature of these factors and the specific determinants of Egypt's energy demand profile. This study stands out as the first in Egypt to address this gap employing a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches, alongside a modelling framework. It fills this significant gap in the existing literature by introducing an integrated model that comprehensively examines both energy demand and supply for Egypt. By identifying the key factors that determine the country's energy demand profile until 2050, this research offers valuable insights into the future energy landscape. It also assesses the economic costs associated with meeting the expected energy demand and evaluates the potential environmental impact of relying

on the current energy mix. To provide practical alternatives, the study also presents empirical evidence on various energy generation scenarios that most effectively align with Egypt's future energy demand while considering climatic factors.

The thesis is divided into four chapters. The first chapter provides an overview of the varied definitions of climate change and highlights key climate change theories. Chapter two delves into the Environmental Economics Theory, demonstrating its role in advancing our economic comprehension of climate change, accompanied by a comprehensive empirical review. Chapter three elaborates on the phenomenon of climate change within the Egyptian context, its drivers and potential impacts, and presents an overview of the energy sector in Egypt. Chapter four presents the methodology, materials, and techniques employed by the study, and introduces the research findings and discussion. The study concludes by summarizing the key findings and their policy implications, offering valuable insights into energy policy decision-making and contributing to an enhanced understanding of the various energy policy options.

Chapter One

Climate Change: A Scientific Perspective

Climate change, commonly termed as and often used synonymously with global warming, is a prominent environmental issue of global scale, which has garnered considerable attention in scientific, policy, and public discourse. At its essence, climate change refers to long-term shifts in weather patterns and average climatic conditions on a global or regional scale, and is characterized by alterations in temperature, precipitation and wind patterns, and other climate variables. However, the scope of climate change extends far beyond these observable alterations, encompassing a broad range of interactions between earth's atmosphere, oceans, land, ice, and living organisms.

1.1. Definitions of Climate Change

Climate change does not offer a singular and/or a universally accepted definition. Instead, its definitions vary depending on a realm of factors including scientific parameters, human-centered perspectives, socioeconomic contexts, and the problem-oriented viewpoint. Each definition provides a unique lens through which we can view and understand this pressing issue.

The scientific definition of climate change is perhaps the most widely recognized. In scientific terms, as endorsed by the IPCC, climate change refers to a shift in global or regional climate patterns, usually observable over extended periods of time, whether spanning decades or even longer durations. These changes are not limited to temperature variations, but also include variations in wind patterns, precipitation, and atmospheric phenomena. This underlines the complexity and far-reaching implications of climate change, extending beyond mere global warming (IPCC, 1990, 1992, 1994, 1995). This definition can be considered of a problem-oriented nature that serves to stir collective action against this looming threat to our planet. However, attributing climate change solely to the scientific domain would be a considerable understatement. A closer look at the definitions proposed by the UNFCCC, reveals a more anthropogenic perspective where climate change is primarily attributed to human activities altering the composition of the earth's atmosphere over comparable time periods. These definitions inherently call for human intervention in mitigating the effects of climate change (UNFCCC, 2015).

Broadening the perspective further, socio-economic definitions of climate change arise. Climate change, in this view, is not just an environmental issue, rather an encumbrance deeply interwoven with social, economic, and political threads. It insinuates that our collective lifestyle choices, forms of governance, and levels of cooperation are pivotal in influencing climate change, projecting a clear image of climate change as a socio-ecological issue (Pigou, 1932; Stern, 2006, 2008; Smith, 2011; Nordhaus, 2013; Dobson, 2015). This definition, consequently, is a driving force for policymaking and decision-making bodies to initiate change. Climate change, therefore, extends beyond just a scientific phenomenon and introduced as an overarching narrative of human decision-making, governance, societal structures and equitable access to resources.

The different definitions of climate change, while adding richness and depth to its understanding, also exemplify the enormity of its scope and scale, and carrying an undeniable common theme that

calls for immediate and profound concern for the environment. Examining these varied definitions is essential to understand climate change's multifaceted character. Each definition offers unique insights and broadens our understanding of climate change as a multidimensional issue, but amidst these diverse viewpoints lies a shared consensus of the need for urgent and effective climate action.

1.2.Underlying Causes of Climate Change

Climate change is primarily and widely accepted as a consequence of human activities that have drastically increased the concentration of greenhouse gases in the earth's atmosphere. These gases trap heat from the sun, causing an increase in the average temperature of our planet. Human activities such as burning fossil fuels for energy, deforestation, industrial processes, and agricultural practices contribute significantly to the rise in GHG emissions. Additionally, the transportation sector, including the use of cars, planes, and ships, releases substantial amounts of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere.

- **Fossil Fuels**

The burning of fossil fuels is the predominant cause of global warming. Coal, oil, and natural gas used extensively for electricity generation, transportation, and industrial processes, are the primary sources of human-induced GHG emissions. When burnt, these fossil fuels release large amounts of CO₂, a notorious greenhouse gas that traps heat in the atmosphere, leading to a rise in global temperature. Between 1990 and 2015, energy consumption was linked to an approximately 52% increase in CO₂ emissions. Further, the energy sector accounted alone for more than 75% of GHG emissions worldwide in 2022 (IEA, 2023).

- **Industrial Processes**

Industrial processes also contribute to warming the globe through the release of various greenhouse gases including CO₂, methane, nitrous oxide, and fluorinated gases, as byproducts of industrial activities. These include chemical reactions necessary to produce goods from raw materials, like the production of cement, iron, and steel, or when synthetic chemicals, such as hydrofluorocarbons used in air conditioners and refrigerators, are released into the atmosphere during manufacturing processes, or by leakage and disposal of the equipment in which they are used (IEA, 2023).

- **Deforestation**

Deforestation, the mass-clearing of trees for various human activities, is an additional major cause of global warming. Forests absorb CO₂ reducing as such the amount of carbon in the atmosphere. When they are cut down, not only does this helpful carbon-absorbing function cease, but the carbon stored in the trees is released back into the atmosphere, leading to a double-edged effect on global warming. It is estimated that deforestation is responsible for about 17% of all human-made global CO₂ emissions (UNEP, 2022).

- **Agriculture**

Agriculture is another key player in global warming contributing about 22% of the total GHG emissions (IPCC, 2019). It is considered a main source of methane, another greenhouse gas that is more potent than CO₂. Methane (CH₄) is primarily produced in the digestive system of ruminants

like cows and sheep and released into the air through their respiration and digestion. Additionally, rice cultivation in flooded fields also emits methane by creating an environment conducive for methane-producing bacteria. Lastly, the excessive use of synthetic fertilizers introduces large amounts of nitrous oxide to the atmosphere (UNEP, 2023).

- **Transportation**

Transportation accounted for 15% of global greenhouse gas emissions in 2019. This sector's emissions primarily stem from the combustion of fossil fuels used in road, rail, air, and marine transport. A significant portion, approximately 95%, of the world's transportation energy is derived from petroleum-based fuels, primarily gasoline and diesel (IPCC, 2019).

- **Buildings**

The buildings sector contributed to 6% of global greenhouse gas emissions in 2019. Emissions from this sector arise from onsite energy generation and the burning of fuels for heating and cooking purposes. It is important to note that if electricity use in buildings is included in this sector, emissions would rise to 16%, rather than being attributed solely to the energy sector (IPCC, 2019).

1.3.Theories of Climate Change

Climate change, with its profound implications for the planet and society, has captured the attention of scientists worldwide. As they strive to unravel its complexities, they have developed various theories that aim to explain its causes and origins. These tireless efforts have provided valuable insights into the mechanisms driving global climate patterns, highlighting the interconnectedness of Earth's systems and the unique challenges the world has recently been facing. In the following section, seven prominent theories that scientists have put forth to decipher the factors contributing to climate change are introduced.

1.3.1. Anthropogenic Global Warming

The Anthropocene, a term increasingly used in both scientific and sociological discussions, refers to a proposed new geological era characterized by profound global effects of human activity on the Earth's ecosystems. Unlike the Holocene, the previous stable period that lasted 12,000 years and allowed human civilizations to develop, the Anthropocene symbolizes a major shift owing to humans' significant impact on the planet. One of the most apparent characteristics of the Anthropocene is the rate and scale of environmental change. Industrialization and population growth have significantly altered more than 77% of the Earth's land outside of Antarctica, leaving an indelible mark on landscapes through deforestation for agriculture, construction of cities, and mining for resources. Ocean acidification and sea-level rise due to climate change is another hallmark. Human activities, particularly the burning of fossil fuels, have sharply increased atmospheric carbon dioxide levels, leading to global warming and consequential changes in the Earth's climate system. These transformations drastically reshape marine and terrestrial habitats alike, altering biodiversity and forcing the extinction of many species at an unnerving rate, a phenomenon referred to as the 'sixth extinction' (Bast, 2010; Lewis & Maslin, 2015).

The impact of this era extends to the Earth's lithosphere, as well. Humans create materials and technologies like plastics, concrete, and nuclear substances that will persist in the geological record for millions of years. These anthropogenic markers provide tangible evidence of the human-forged epoch and will be a future indicator of a decidedly Anthropogenic stratigraphy. However, the notion of the Anthropocene is not limited to environmental changes; it conveys crucial sociopolitical messages as well. It underlines the urgency to acknowledge that humans are no longer interacting with nature from a distance but are an inseparable part of the Earth system. This paradigm shift invites different approach towards our responsibility to the planet and each other, urging the convergence of environmental sustainability with economic considerations and social fairness; a principle defining the broad ambitions of the SDGs (McDermid & Winter, 2017).

Despite the Anthropocene's influence, naming this era however does not signify an end. Rather, it stimulates recognition of a crisis, potentially spurring action to mitigate further harm to the earth's systems. Importantly, human agency, the very actor driving the Anthropocene, is capable of moderating these changes through conscious and sustainable practices. The Anthropocene is therefore a stark reminder that the rapidly rising environmental concerns are not isolated events but part of a larger global transformative process that demands immediate and collective action from all humankind. Hence, the Anthropocene epoch is both an objective geological reality and a subjective cultural awakening.

1.3.2. Solar Variability

Solar variability refers to changes in the amount and distribution of solar radiation emitted by the Sun. These variations occur on various time scales, from short-term fluctuations, such as solar flares and sunspots, to long-term changes over thousands or millions of years (Maslin, 2021). This theory is built on the assumption that solar radiation is a primary driver of Earth's climate, providing the energy that fuels atmospheric circulation, drives weather patterns, and influences the Earth's energy balance. It suggests further that fluctuations in solar output, such as changes in the sun's eleven-year sunspot cycles or longer-term cycles, can impact climate systems on Earth.

While solar variability plays an evident role in influencing climate, its overall contribution to recent global warming has been relatively small compared to the impact of greenhouse gases. Long-term solar variability, such as changes in solar output over millennia, can affect climate patterns and natural climate oscillations, but attributing specific climate changes solely to solar activity is difficult due to the presence of other factors (Vázquez, 2004). Scientists study solar variability using a range of techniques, including measurements of total solar irradiance, proxy records from geological archives, satellite observations, and models that simulate the Sun's behavior, which help understand how solar variability influences the climate system, improve climate predictions, and place recent climate changes in a broader context.

1.3.3. Planetary Motion

The Planetary Motion theory argues that the motion and position of the Earth in its orbit around the Sun, known as planetary motion, influence climate through various mechanisms. These include the changes in solar radiation received by different parts of the Earth over time scales ranging from seasons to millennia. One of the fundamental drivers of climate change associated with the

planetary motion theorem is the Milankovitch cycles. These natural variations arise from changes in the Earth's orbit, axial tilt, and precession. The timing and magnitude of these cycles modulate the distribution of solar radiation on Earth, impacting the amount of energy received seasonally and latitudinally.

There are three primary Milankovitch cycles, eccentricity, obliquity, and precession. Eccentricity refers to the shape of Earth's orbit around the Sun, ranging from more elliptical to more circular over approximately hundred-thousand years. Obliquity denotes changes in Earth's axial tilt, varying between 22.1-24.5 degrees over a period of about forty-thousand years. Precession refers to the wobbling motion of Earth's axis, resulting in slight shifts in the position of the equinoxes and solstices over a period of approximately twenty-six thousand years (Bast, 2010; Maslin, 2021). These variations in the planetary motion can impact the seasonal and latitudinal distribution of solar radiation, influencing the intensity, timing, and location of climate patterns. While the Milankovitch cycles themselves do not cause climate change, they can act as a forcing mechanism, initiating feedback processes in the climate system, such as changes in ice coverage, greenhouse gas concentrations, and atmospheric circulation. Understanding the influence of planetary motion on climate and disentangling its effects from other factors, such as greenhouse gas concentrations, is a challenging task. Researchers employ a combination of climate models, paleoclimatic data, and observations to better understand and quantify the role of planetary motion in past, present, and future climate changes.

1.3.4. Cloud Formation and Albedo

Cloud formation and its impact on the planet's albedo, the measure of how reflective a surface or an object is, representing the fraction of incoming sunlight or solar radiation that is reflected back into space, constitute a crucial element in the Earth's climate system. Clouds can both absorb and reflect incoming solar radiation, causing significant changes in the planet's energy balance and thus influencing climate patterns. Clouds primarily form through the condensation of water vapor around microscopic particles in the atmosphere, called cloud condensation nuclei (CCN). These CCN can be derived from various sources including natural aerosols like dust, sea salt, and biogenic particles, as well as human-produced aerosols such as pollution. The albedo of clouds or their ability to reflect incoming sunlight largely depends on their droplet size, liquid water content, and altitude. Low-level clouds, such as stratocumulus clouds, generally have a high albedo, whereas high-level clouds, like cirrus clouds, tend to have a lower albedo.

The overall impact of clouds on climate is highly complex, involving interactions between cloud cover, height, and composition. Changes in cloud cover and properties can either amplify or dampen the effects of climate change. For instance, an increase in cloud cover resulting from higher atmospheric moisture content can enhance the greenhouse effect, leading to additional warming. On the other hand, alterations in cloud properties, such as increased reflectivity due to more abundant and smaller cloud droplets, can have a cooling effect by reflecting more sunlight back into space (Bast, 2010). Understanding the intricate processes of cloud formation, their interaction with aerosols, and their influence on climate remains an active area of research. Advances in satellite observations, ground-based measurements, and climate modelling aim to unravel complexities of cloud-climate feedbacks and improve the accuracy of climate predictions.

1.3.5. Ocean Currents

Ocean currents play a critical role in regulating the distribution of heat around the globe, influencing regional and global climate patterns via transporting vast amounts of energy, redistributing heat from the tropics towards higher latitudes and moderating the planet's climate. This theory proposes that large-scale ocean currents, such as the Gulf Stream and the North Atlantic Drift, are driven by a combination of wind, temperature gradients, and Earth's rotation, as a result, changes in ocean currents can have significant implications for the Earth's climate.

The most prominent example of ocean currents' impact on climate is the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC), also known as the Atlantic conveyor belt. The AMOC transports warm surface waters from the tropics to the North Atlantic region, where they release heat into the atmosphere and moderate temperatures. This process helps maintain a relatively mild climate in northern Europe. Disruptions or weakening of the AMOC can lead to significant regional climate changes, such as reduced thermal gradients and altered precipitation patterns.

Several factors can influence ocean currents, including wind patterns, temperature gradients, and variations in salinity. These factors are interconnected and affect the density and flow of water masses, thereby influencing the strength and direction of ocean currents. Changes in atmospheric circulation, such as shifts in wind patterns due to climate change, can impact ocean currents and alter heat transfer across the globe (Bast, 2010).

Understanding the dynamics of ocean currents is vital for accurate climate modelling and predictions. Scientists use both direct measurements from instruments like buoys and ships, as well as remote sensing techniques like satellite observations and oceanographic moorings. By monitoring and analyzing ocean currents, researchers can better comprehend climate variability, improve climate models, and enhance our ability to assess future impacts of climate change.

1.3.6. Bio-thermostat

The bio-thermostat theory proposes that Earth's climate is regulated by biological processes through the feedback mechanisms of living organisms. It suggests that various organisms, particularly marine phytoplankton, play a significant role in controlling global temperatures. Specifically, this theory states that the production of dimethyl sulfide (DMS) by phytoplankton in the oceans contributes to the formation of cloud condensation nuclei (CCN). When DMS is released into the atmosphere, it oxidizes to form sulfate aerosols, which serve as CCN. These aerosols, in turn, influence cloud formation and properties, affecting the planet's albedo and thereby its energy balance (Maslin, 2021).

The bio-thermostat theory argues that the increased production of DMS by phytoplankton, in response to rising temperatures, leads to the formation of more clouds and therefore increased cloud cover. This increased cloud cover reflects more sunlight back into space and results in a negative feedback mechanism that ultimately regulates temperature (Bast, 2010).

However, while this theory is intriguing, the role of bio-thermostat in climate regulation is still not fully understood and is subject to ongoing scientific research. Further studies are needed to better understand the interactions between marine ecosystems, cloud-forming processes, and their impact on Earth's climate system.

1.3.7. Human Forcings besides Greenhouse Gases

While greenhouse gases are widely recognized as the primary driver of anthropogenic climate change, human activities also contribute to climate change through several other mechanisms. These additional factors are often referred to as human forcings, and include various direct and indirect influences on the global climate system.

One prominent example of a human forcing is the emission of aerosols, both natural and anthropogenic. Aerosols can have both warming and cooling effects depending on their composition, size, and location. For instance, black carbon aerosols from fossil fuel combustion tend to absorb sunlight, leading to localized warming, while sulfate aerosols from industrial activities can scatter sunlight and contribute to cooling. Land use and land cover changes resulting from human activities, such as deforestation and urbanization, also influence climate patterns. These changes affect the absorption and reflection of solar radiation, alter surface roughness, and impact regional weather patterns. Deforestation, in particular, reduces carbon sinks, leading to increased atmospheric CO₂ concentrations. Other human forcings include alterations to the nitrogen and phosphorus cycles, changes in atmospheric pollution levels, and modification of the Earth's surface through the construction of infrastructure. Each of these human activities has the potential to significantly affect regional and global climate patterns (Bast, 2010; Maslin, 2021).

In conclusion, ocean currents, planetary motion, and solar variability are all significant factors that influence climate patterns. While greenhouse gases are the primary driver of anthropogenic climate change, understanding these natural drivers is crucial for comprehending past climate variations, improving climate modeling, and making more accurate predictions about future climate changes.

1.4. Potential Impact of Climate Change

Climate change is a pressing global issue with its effects permeating across multiple sectors. Rising temperatures, altered precipitation patterns, sea-level rise, and extreme weather events collectively contribute to changing the world climate, and puts ecosystems worldwide under immense pressure. These changes have profound repercussions that necessitate thorough investigation to understand their nature and magnitude. Instances of potential consequences of climate change include:

1.4.1. Shifts in Temperature and Precipitation Patterns

Climate change can cause disruption of temperature and precipitation patterns that adversely affect biodiversity, ecosystem structure, and species distributions, and cause changes in habitats and phenology which interrupts ecological interactions and potentially leading to species extinctions. Moreover, climate change-induced ocean acidification further threatens marine ecosystems and the services they support (IPCC, 2019).

1.4.2. Challenges to Global Water Resources

Changing precipitation patterns and increased evapotranspiration impact water availability, quality, and distribution. This affects freshwater ecosystems, agricultural productivity, and human livelihoods. Changes in the timing and intensity of rainfall can lead to more frequent and severe droughts, as well as increased risk of flooding in some regions. Water scarcity exacerbates societal tensions and can lead to conflicts over limited resources.

1.4.3. Challenges for Agricultural Systems

Agricultural systems are also highly sensitive to climate change, impacting food security and rural livelihoods. Shifts in temperature and rainfall patterns alter growing seasons, crop yields, and pest dynamics. Extreme weather events such as heatwaves, droughts, and floods can decimate agricultural production, affecting both subsistence and commercial farming. Changes in crop suitability may require significant transformations in agricultural practices and land-use patterns to maintain productivity and adapt to new climates (UNEP, 2022).

1.4.4. Negative Impacts on Human Health

Climate change directly and indirectly affects human health in various ways. Heatwaves can lead to heat-related illnesses and mortality, while changing patterns of infectious diseases, such as malaria and dengue, are influenced by shifts in vector distribution and behavior. Air pollution, exacerbated by higher temperatures, intensifies respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. Disrupted food systems and increased food insecurity also impact nutritional outcomes and exacerbate malnutrition. Vulnerable populations, including the elderly, children, and marginalized communities, suffer disproportionately from these health impacts. Furthermore, the impacts of climate change are projected to result in an approximate annual increase of 250,000 deaths between 2030 to 2050, and an estimated annual direct cost ranging from \$2-4 billion by 2030. Furthermore, climate change can exacerbate the preexisting barriers that hinder healthcare access, particularly during critical periods and undermines the achievement of universal health coverage (World Health Organization (WHO), 2021).

1.4.5. Energy Systems Disruptions

The energy sector is particularly vulnerable to effects induced by climate change. Rising temperatures and increased heatwaves generate higher energy demand and consumption, especially for cooling purposes, placing further strain on electricity grids to meet the power needs of households, businesses, and industries, and requires additional energy generation and distribution capacity (IPCC, 2014). Moreover, while it may seem counterintuitive, climate change can also stimulate increased coldness and very low temperatures in certain regions, which also puts an additional pressure on energy systems due to higher energy demand and consumption for heating purposes. One of the ways in which this can manifest is when climate change weakens the polar vortex, a large whirlwind of frigid air that typically remains confined to the polar regions and cause its interruption, pushing by this colder air from the Arctic towards lower latitudes and resulting in unusually cold and severe winter conditions (Holdren, 2014; NASA, 2023d).

Climate change can also have a substantial impact on various energy generation processes that rely on water for cooling and other essential purposes. The altered precipitation patterns and shifts in water availability caused by climate change can lead to decreased river flows and exacerbated water shortages. These conditions ultimately impose limitations on the operation of thermoelectric power plants, which in turn affects energy production and reliability. Furthermore, energy infrastructure including power plants, transmission lines, and fuel storage facilities, is highly

vulnerable to extreme weather events such as storms, floods, and sea-level rise, which can easily damage this infrastructure causing power outages and supply disruptions (King & Gullede, 2014).

1.4.6. Climate-Induced Migration

Climate change-induced migration is a significant consequence of the changing climate, as individuals and communities are forced to relocate due to the adverse impacts of environmental degradation and climate-related hazards. In such contexts, climate change acts as a threat multiplier in human migration, exacerbating existing vulnerabilities and pushing individuals and communities to seek safer and more sustainable living conditions (Vinke et al., 2020).

Climate-induced migration is a multifaceted phenomenon influenced by socioeconomic, political, and environmental factors. This phenomenon occurs particularly when climate change acts as a catalyst for migration by amplifying existing drivers and creating new ones. For instance, environmental degradation including drought, sea-level rise, desertification, and other extreme weather events that severely affect livelihoods, food security, water resources, and ecosystems. Displacement may also arise from slow-onset changes, such as gradual sea-level rise, which render areas uninhabitable over time. These environmental stressors intertwine with socioeconomic factors, political instability, and conflicts, compounding the drivers of migration. Internal migration within countries is often the most common response to climate change impacts, as individuals move from rural to urban areas or from affected regions to more stable regions within the same country. Nevertheless, climate change also drives cross-border migration either through regular migration channels or as a result of displacement and seeking asylum. These patterns of migration are influenced by economic disparities, political factors, geographic proximity, and social networks (Baldwin et al., 2019; Boas et al., 2022; Lunstrum & Bose, 2022).

The impacts of climate-induced migration are complex and multifaceted, affecting migrants, host communities, and the regions of origin. The social, economic, and political implications of migration can be both positive and negative. Migrants often face challenges in adapting to new social contexts, finding livelihood opportunities, accessing healthcare, and integrating into host communities. Host communities may also experience social tensions, competition over resources, and strains on infrastructure and services. Furthermore, regions of origin may suffer from the loss of skilled labor, reduced social cohesion, and a loss of cultural heritage.

1.4.7. Unpredictable Climate Patterns

As GHG emissions continue to rise, significant alternations in climatic patterns across the globe are developing. One notable manifestation of this phenomenon is the influence of climate change on the occurrence of El Niño and La Niña climate patterns. Traditionally, El Niño and La Niña, also known as El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) cycle, are cyclical patterns that occur in the tropical Pacific Ocean, originating from complex interactions between the atmosphere and tropical ocean waters. El Niño events are characterized by unusually warm ocean surface temperatures in the eastern Pacific, which can influence atmospheric circulation and alter weather patterns worldwide. Conversely, La Niña events are marked by cooler ocean temperatures in the eastern Pacific, leading to distinct atmospheric conditions (National Oceanic and Atmospheric

Administration (NOAA), 2023). Climate change influences El Niño and La Niña by amplifying the underlying oceanic and atmospheric conditions that fuel these phenomena. Warmer oceans due to climate change provide additional energy and moisture to the atmosphere, intensifying the strength and impact of El Niño events. This results in heightened rainfall and increased likelihood of extreme weather events such as floods, storms, and droughts in various regions. On the other hand, La Niña events can also become more pronounced under climate change, leading to enhanced variability in weather patterns, including prolonged dry spells and increased risk of wildfires. A recent report by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) is expecting a significant rise to new records for global temperatures in the upcoming five years. The foreseen increase in temperature, according to the report, is attributed to the effects of heat-retaining greenhouse gases coupled with the natural onset of an El Niño event (WMO, 2023).

Beyond local impacts, El Niño has the potential to prompt a range of impacts across the globe. It can influence the global climate system, affecting atmospheric circulation patterns and, consequently, weather conditions in distant regions. For example, several studies have shown the correlation between El Niño and changes in the Indian monsoon systems, often known as South Asian monsoon, leading to altered precipitation patterns across the Indian subcontinent (Ashok & Tejavath, 2019; Dandi et al., 2020; Lenka et al., 2022; Park et al., 2010; Sahu et al., 2022; Sooraj et al., 2023; Zhang & Li, 2023). While the specific effects can vary depending on the intensity and duration of the event, there are several general patterns associated with El Niño that have been observed in the past. One significant potential impact of El Niño is the alteration of weather patterns. In many regions, El Niño can bring about increased rainfall, resulting in flooding and higher-than-normal precipitation, while other areas may experience reduced rainfall and drought conditions. These changes in precipitation can have significant implications for agriculture, water resources, and ecosystem health (NOAA, 2023).

Another likely impact of El Niño is that it can lead to higher temperatures in some regions. This can affect everything from agricultural yields to human health, especially in areas prone to heatwaves such as Eastern and Southern Africa, the Horn of Africa, Latin America and the Caribbean, and the Asia-Pacific region. These regions were severely affected by intense drought and resulting food insecurity, alongside flooding, heavy rainfall, and elevated temperatures caused by a previous episode of El Niño in 2016, during which a myriad of health issues have risen including malnutrition, dehydration, heat stress, respiratory ailments, and disease outbreak (WHO, 2016). Therefore, they are expected to be particularly vulnerable to impacts of a similar or stronger El Niño occurrence. A strong El Niño event has the potential to contribute an increase of approximately 0.2 degrees Celsius to average global temperature, suggests that the earth's temperatures can exceed the 1.5 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels threshold outlined in the Paris Agreement, taking into account the 1.2 degrees Celsius increase of the earth's temperature above the 1850-1900 average (World Meteorological Organization (WMO), 2023).

In terms of marine ecosystems, El Niño can disrupt the productivity and distribution of marine organisms. The warming of ocean waters can cause shifts in nutrient availability, leading to changes in the abundance and distribution of fish stocks. Coral reefs, in particular, are vulnerable

to El Niño events, as warmer waters can lead to widespread coral bleaching, damaging these delicate ecosystems (Eddy et al., 2021; Hughes et al., 2018; Spiecker & Menge, 2022).

1.5. Climate Change and Sustainable Development

Climate change is one of the most significant challenges facing humanity in the twenty-first century. The increasing global temperatures, rising sea-level, extreme weather events, and loss of biodiversity are all clear indications of the urgency to address this issue. In response, the international community has set forth the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as a framework to mitigate climate change and achieve sustainable development. The SDGs were adopted by the United Nations in 2015, with the aim to create a more sustainable and prosperous future for all. These goals recognize the interconnectedness of social, economic, and environmental dimensions of development and provide a blueprint for action to tackle the most pressing global challenges, including climate change (International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD), 2023). The undeniable essence of sustainable development revolves around socioeconomic growth while preserving the planet for future generations. The climate crisis is redefining this narrative. This section aims to bridge the gap between climate change and sustainable development via demonstrating how addressing climate change paves the way for sustainable development.

Climate change is the defining issue of our time, with temperature increase, sea-level rise, more frequent extremes, irregular rainfalls, trying to wreck our ecosystems, and potentially threatening our survival. The link between climate change and human activities, predominantly the combustion of fossil fuels, has irreversibly compromised the earth's natural balance. The concept of sustainable development, as outlined in the Brundtland groundbreaking environmental report published in 1987 by the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED), refers to a form of development that satisfies present needs while safeguarding the capacity of future generations to fulfill their own needs. This holistic approach encompasses three fundamental pillars; economic, social, and environmental sustainability (United Nations, 2020).

Climate change poses formidable challenges to sustainable development. It intensifies world hunger, health, water scarcity, inequality, and extreme poverty, compounding the problem of sustainable development. However, the link between warming temperatures and these multiple sectors offers pathways to prospects. Addressing climate change, the chief catalyst of these challenges, would directly contribute to sustainable development. The correlation between climate change mitigation strategies and sustainable efforts is inherent. Renewable energy, energy efficiency, climate-smart agriculture, and green urban planning are a few facets where this convergence becomes evident. Transitioning from a carbon-intensive economy to a neutrality-seeking one, renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, hydropower, and geothermal have emerged as the frontrunners, aligning with the seventh goal of the SDGs, 'Affordable and Clean Energy' (McCollum et al., 2018; Bertheau, 2020).

Climate-smart agriculture that aims for sustainable food production, the increase of farmers' resilience to climate change, and mitigation of emissions addresses the second goal of 'Zero Hunger' and the thirteenth goal of 'Climate Action'. Moreover, promoting a green economy and maintaining ecological urbanization would candidly lead to the achievement of a 'Responsible

Consumption and Production’ which is the twelfth goal of the SDGs. Green jobs that the climate change mitigation strategies aim to foster work towards the achievement of the first goal of the SDGs; ‘alleviating Poverty’, and ensure a ‘Decent Work and Economic Growth,’ the eighth goal. Finally, linking climate change and sustainable development urges reframing previous perspectives and developing innovative pathways for both mitigation and adaptation, while melding them into sustainable development objectives. The potential benefits are diverse, ranging from enhanced energy security and improved public health to poverty reduction and social development. However, the intent is not to paint an easy road to sustainable development while combating climate change. It's about realizing the inevitable intertwining of the two and embedding this understanding into our global strategies, harnessing the synergies between them and turning a global risk into a chance to re-model our economies onto a sustainable path.

Chapter Two

Theoretical Framework for Climate Change

Introduction

A crucial aspect of modern economic discourse is exploring the interplay between the economy and the environment. From an economic perspective, the environment offers a wealth of resources that feed the production and consumption processes. Nevertheless, the same processes often lead to environmental degradation and threaten sustainability. Economic activities derive from, and impact upon, our natural environment. The environment provides raw materials, such as minerals, timber, and water, that are crucial to economic production. At the same time, it acts as a sink for the wastes produced during economic activities. The finite nature of resources and the limited capacity of ecosystems to absorb waste underline the intricate relationship between the environment and the economy (Nordhaus, 2013).

One of the areas in which the economy-environment relationship is most apparent is in the '*Tragedy of The Commons*', a situation in which individuals acting independently according to their self-interest behave contrary to the common good by depleting or spoiling shared resources. This principle is evident in issues such as overfishing or deforestation. From an economic standpoint, it is a clear example of market failure, necessitating intervention to provide the correct incentives for sustainable resource usage.

Another perspective that rests on the argument that economic growth, manifested through heightened production and consumption, inevitably leads to environmental degradation is the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC). ECK is a graphical representation of the relationship between income per capita and environmental degradation that embarks on this discussion (Smith, 2011; Nordhaus, 2013). According to EKC, environmental degradation follows an inverted U-path as economic development occurs. At the initial stages of development, people prioritize economic growth over environmental preservation, causing environmental degradation. However, as income per capita increases and societal attitudes evolve, an increased emphasis is placed on environmental protection, which drives environmental improvement. The EKC also assumes that environmental damage can be reversed, which is not always the case as some forms of degradation are irreversible. However, the EKC has been criticized for its over-simplistic representation of the relationship between economic growth and environmental degradation.

Moreover, economics can provide essential tools and solutions to achieve sustainable development. Principles such as externalities, where the cost or benefit of an activity affects others not involved in the activity, along with the 'polluter pays' principle can help to align economic growth with environmental protection. Policies like setting corrective tax to confront CO₂ emissions, introducing tradeable emissions permits, or subsidizing renewable energies are examples of economic instruments used globally to counter environmental degradation. Meanwhile, developments in fields like green and circular economics point out that environmental sustainability and economic prosperity can go hand-in-hand. Green economics argues for an

economic system that is fully integrated with and respects the ecosystem, focusing on sustainable development, while circular economics promotes an economic system aimed at eliminating waste and the continuous use of resources (Smith, 2011). Hence, while there is no denying that economic activities affect the environment, under the right circumstances, the economy can also serve as a tool for achieving environmental sustainability. As such, the interplay between the economy and the environment must be met with an effective mix of informed policymaking, innovative economic practices, and proactive societal participation for a sustainable future.

This chapter answers one of the three sub-questions posed by the study; *“How can climate change be explained through the lens of environmental economics theory?”* The discussion begins with an examination of the theory of externalities, tracing its origins to Arthur C. Pigou and his foundational insights into market inefficiencies resulting from external costs. It delves deeper into the implications of both positive and negative externalities, illustrating how recognizing these factors is essential for shaping effective public policy and guiding economic practices. Building on this foundation, the chapter transitions to the principles of environmental economics, emphasizing how this crucial subfield addresses environmental degradation through a diverse range of analytical tools and sustainable development strategies. Furthermore, the chapter underlines the imperative of integrating climate change considerations into environmental economics theory, illustrating how this integration not only tackles environmental challenges but also fosters sustainable growth. To enrich the discussion, the chapter presents an empirical framework that explores energy modelling and alternative energy scenarios, showcasing how these methodologies can inform policy decisions and advance sustainable practices.

2.1.Theory of Externalities

The theory of externalities, also known as the theory of external costs or benefits, is a fundamental concept in economics. It refers to the impact of one individual's actions on the wellbeing of others, for which the individual does not bear the full cost or enjoy the full benefit. The concept of externalities in economics was actually first introduced by the economist Arthur C. Pigou in 1920, when he first developed the theory of externalities and discussed how external costs or benefits that are imposed on third parties can lead to market inefficiencies. He argued that these externalities could and should be corrected through government intervention, such as through the use of taxes or subsidies. Pigou's work on externalities was instrumental in shaping the field of welfare economics and had a significant impact on economic research and policymaking.

In economic theory, an externality refers to a condition where the actions of one party, either individuals or corporations, have an indirect impact on others who are not involved in that particular transaction or situation. These impacts, which can be positive or negative, usually occur when the private cost or benefit of an economic activity differs from the societal cost or benefit. Externalities are a quintessential illustration of market failure, a circumstance where free markets struggle to allocate resources efficiently, warranting an intervention for correction.

Externalities can be either positive or negative. Positive externalities occur when one person's activities benefit others without compensation. Positive externalities occur when a product or action results in benefits to third parties who did not choose to incur that benefit. An example is

when a homeowner plants beautiful flowers in their garden, which improves the aesthetic value of the neighborhood. The classic example of a positive externality also includes the creation of knowledge; when an individual invents a new product, society can freely utilize the knowledge of that invention at no additional cost. This information spillover leads to the under-production of knowledge from a societal standpoint as the inventors cannot capture the full benefits of the innovation (Pigou, 1932).

Negative externalities, on the other hand, result in costs imposed on others without compensation or when an individual/business making decision does not have to pay the full cost of the decision. If a good has a negative externality, then the cost to society is greater than the cost the consumer is paying for it. Common examples of negative externalities include air and water pollution, overfishing, traffic congestion, and others. In the case of pollution, if a factory produces goods for sale; in the process of manufacturing, it also emits harmful chemicals into the environment. During the manufacturing of goods, the producer factors in the private costs such as labor wages, raw materials, energy, etc. however, they do not take into account the cost inflicted upon the society due to pollution, degraded air quality, and health damages among community members. The costs borne by the society are external to the factory's cost calculations, hence termed an externality.

There is a well-known remedy for externalities within economics which is the Pigouvian tax or subsidy. A Pigouvian tax bares the way for internalizing an externality. In the case of negative externalities, a tax equal to the external cost per unit can be levied on the goods. For instance, a per unit tax on pollutants emitted by a factory will align the private cost of production with the social cost. Hence, the producers will reduce output to what is socially optimal when they bear this tax (Pigou, 1932). A Pigouvian subsidy, as a flip side, is designed to handle positive externalities. If public benefits exceed private returns, society will less likely produce due to the inability to capture the full benefits. A subsidy equal to the value of the externality can stimulate production up to the level that equates social benefit with social cost.

While Pigouvian taxes and subsidies theoretically demonstrate the ability to align private incentives with public welfare, in practice, their implementation can be challenging. Identifying and adequately measuring external effects, determining the right level of tax or subsidy, and effectively implementing it are all substantial tasks. From an economist's standpoint, one may argue for the Coase theorem as an alternate course. The theorem, offered by Nobel laureate Ronald Coase, suggests that if transaction costs are low and property rights well-defined, negotiations between parties would result in an efficient solution, irrespective of who initially owns those rights (Nordhaus, 2013). Notwithstanding the complexities of externalities and policies around them, public discourse and action related to these issues have never been more pertinent. Currently, pressing challenges such as climate change, public health, and digital rights are all burdened with external costs and/or impacts. As we progress, understanding externalities, both at micro- and macroeconomic levels, will continue to be a pivotal part of the approach to these challenges (Smith, 2011).

The versatility and applicability of the externality concept underlines its prominence in the economic theory. Simultaneously, building full-proof measures to address these in reality will

continue to put the economic rationale to the test and drive innovations in policy designing. While the theory of externalities intersects multiple disciplines of economic thought, from environmental economics to public finance, it also opens a window to review, question, and redefine notions of cost, benefit, welfare, and social justice within an economic framework.

2.2.Environmental Economics Theory

Environmental economics is a groundbreaking subfield of economics that addresses fundamental economic questions in light of our symbiotic relationship with the natural world. Environmental economic theory provides both a theoretical and practical framework for understanding the intricate connections between economic activity, environmental quality, and human wellbeing. In many ways, building on the theory of externalities, environmental economics seeks to analyze and address the external costs, or negative externalities, associated with environmental degradation, and distinctively portrays how these costs impact overall societal welfare.

Environmental economics extends the theory of externalities by incorporating aspects of the environment into the analysis of market failure. Recognizing that many environmental resources are public goods with no assigned property rights or market price, environmental economists use various tools such as hedonic pricing, travel cost method, and contingent valuation to estimate the economic value of these resources. Such valuation allows for better-informed policy decisions and more accurate assessments of the societal cost-benefit analysis, thus addressing and internalizing externalities. *'Tragedy of the Commons'* is a crucial concept explored in environmental economics which reflects a situation where individuals, acting in their self-interest, deplete shared resource, leaving less for future generations. This predicament captures large-scale environmental issues like overfishing, deforestation, and climate change, effectively demonstrating how unregulated markets can lead to resources overuse, tying directly to the concept of negative externalities (Stern, 2006, 2008; Smith 2011; Nordhaus, 2013).

Addressing these negative externalities and market failures is not a straightforward task. Environmental economists examine various policy tools to help correct these outcomes. These tools include command-and-control regulations, tax and subsidy measures, and tradable permit systems, which are designed to reflect the full cost of resource use and incentivize the reduction of environmental harm, essentially suggesting policy maneuvers to internalize the externalities, a concept we initially encountered in the realm of the externality theory. One of the significant contributions of the environmental economics theory is the promotion and rigorous conceptualization of sustainable development. Key issues here involve determining optimal rates of resource use, the choice of technology in production and consumption, and the distribution and equity considerations of resource usage across current and future generations.

The concept of sustainable development exemplifies the ideal that synchronization between economic and environmental goals is not only desirable but also achievable. Environmental economics also focuses on the conceptualization of the environment as natural capital and the economic interpretation of ecological services. Natural Capital refers to the stock of natural resources like air, water, soil, minerals, and biological diversity that provide flows of useful goods and/or services (Smith, 2011). Ecological Services are the gains received by humanity from the

ecosystem such as air and water purification, carbon sequestration, pollination, and many more. Recognizing and assessing the economic value of these often-overlooked services is crucial to inform policy decisions and account for environmental externalities more holistically.

- **Integrating Climate Change into Environmental Economic Theory**

While traditional economic theory seldom integrates environmental concerns, the new era calls for a reconsideration through the lens of environmental economics. This economic field, considering environmental resources as a part of economic variables, brings a radical shift in how we perceive production, consumption, and growth (Stern, 2008). Environmental economics is the study of how economy and the environment interact. A fundamental aim of the field is addressing problems such as climate change through the integration of environmental concerns into the mainstream of economic policy. Hence, altering traditional economic theory requires a new and multifaceted approach that involves redefining economic growth and welfare. Traditional models have always measured welfare using GDP, which often does not account for environmental degradation. It is imperative therefore to develop new models that factor renewable and non-renewable sources into the equation (Nordhaus, 2013).

This transformation shall provide a broader perspective on actual economic growth, reflecting the associated environmental costs. In this context, the concept of Green GDP introduces a possible alternative measure that factors in environmental costs and benefits into national income, accounting the sum of the value-added by all producers in the economy. GDP as such represents economic growth while considering the ecosystem services used and/or affected by that growth.

On the other hand, the principles of Polluter Pays and User Pays stand central to environmental economics. These principles can be efficiently administrated through market-based instruments, like an environmental tax, in order to encourage a reduction in pollutant emission or resource exhaustion. A carbon tax is one of these taxes, where each unit of CO₂ emission gets taxed. Such market-based mechanisms internalize environmental costs and bridge the gap between private costs and social costs. Furthermore, integrating climate considerations into economic theory lies in incentivizing environmentally friendly practices. Incentives both in the form of subsidies for environmentally friendly processes, products, or punishing pollution and wastage encourage businesses to follow sustainable practices. Such a system makes it financially sustainable to prioritize the environment, yielding a healthier environment and a thriving economy.

The inclusion of non-market valuation of environmental goods and services is also an essential aspect of environmental economics. Many natural resources like air, water, or biodiversity are considered public goods. Their value is rarely reflected in the market transactions. Conducting non-market valuation studies can help establish a monetary value to these public goods. The contingent valuation, choice experiments and hedonic pricing are some of the more popular methods in this field (Smith, 2011). This valuation would help governments and businesses to understand the true cost and benefits of their actions concerning these resources.

Lastly, fostering cross-border cooperation is vital in combating climate change, a problem not confined by geographic boundaries. Mitigation and adaptation efforts to climate change call for global collaboration. Countries should negotiate and work together to set pollution limits and

devise economic measures in line with these limits (UNFCCC, 2015). In the face of imminent climate change threats, integrating climate impacts into economic theories is critical. Recognizing the economic value of our natural resources is vital for sustainable development. The environmental economic approach can provide us with a roadmap to achieve sustainable economic growth without compromising our environment. Only through bridging the gap between the environment and economics, we can promote sound policies in the fight against climate change.

2.3. Empirical Framework

Energy modelling and the exploration of alternative energy mix scenarios have captivated the attention of researchers across various disciplines due to its significant implications for energy planning, policy design, and sustainable development. Several scholars have undertaken the task of categorizing energy models based on their analytical approach, dividing them into three groups, namely top-down, bottom-up, and integrated or hybrid models. Bottom-up models discuss thoroughly energy generating technologies, but it lacks practical details necessary for making final policy decisions. On the other hand, top-down models effectively mitigate this limitation by incorporating macroeconomic feedback, however they cannot reliably forecast future market responses, mostly attributed to their inherent deficiency in incorporating technology specific details. The disparity between the two models created the need for an integrated model that combine features from both frameworks (Bhattacharyya & Timilsina, 2010; Herbst et al., 2012; Neshat et al., 2014; Schinko et al., 2017; Subramanian et al., 2018; Hawker & Bell, 2020).

- **Integrated (Hybrid) Energy Models**

Scholarly efforts have therefore been directed towards specific areas that align with this classification in most cases with a prevailing emphasis on both the integrated and bottom-up approaches. Jacobsen (1998) introduced a comprehensive model that combined the features of both top-down and bottom-up energy models and applied it extensively in the Danish context. Ringkjøb et al. (2018) utilized the LEAP system as an integrated platform for energy analysis and planning spanning a time horizon of 20 to 50 years. The research conducted by Vieira et al. (2020) serves as an illustration of how the integration of bottom-up and top-down approaches can be achieved. In their work, they presented a framework for energy preservation policy, which effectively combined elements from both approaches. Moreover, the study conducted by Yang et al. (2021) examined the integration of the top-down Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model with the bottom-up pollutant control model, to assess the effects of decarbonization on energy, economic, and ecological variables in China.

- **Bottom-Up Energy Models**

Other strands of literature investigated the inherent differences among the various energy models to examine the implications of these variations on the accuracy, reliability, and policy relevance of the model outputs. Park et al. (2016) used a bottom-up model to evaluate the electrical energy production in South Korea. Their study involved calculating the optimal portfolio, considering renewable energy technologies explicitly, up until 2050, with the cost-effectiveness of measures being assessed. Prina et al. (2020) performed a comprehensive assessment of the categorization

algorithms used in modelling bottom-up energy systems. Their findings showed that the Market Allocation and The Integrated MARKAL-EFOM System (MARKAL/TIMES) and the Open-Source Energy Modelling Systems (OSeMOSYS) were observed to possess somewhat lower temporal and techno-economic data resolutions, while exhibiting moderate spatial resolutions. On the other hand, the LEAP model underwent an evaluation as a long-term energy model characterized by comparatively lower resolutions in terms of temporal, spatial, and techno-economic variables.

In a similar vein, Perissi et al. (2021) conducted a study aiming to evaluate the performance of the Modelling Energy System Development under Environmental and Socioeconomic Constraints (MEDEAS) in conjunction with The Integrated Markal-EFOM System (TIMES) and LEAP models to examine the dynamics of the Austria's and Bulgaria's energy transition. According to the findings, the three models effectively simulated scenarios in replicating past patterns, however, a significant discrepancy was detected with the introduction of renewables at certain degrees. Furthermore, Prina et al. (2021) conducted a thorough analysis of the available bottom-up models where they evaluated and compared forty-three different studies that utilized these models for analysis at national level. Sanchez et al. (2021) conducted a study to assess the role of bottom-up energy models in informing policy formulation for enhancing residential building and sector-specific electricity end-use efficiency. The findings showed that models constructed using a bottom-up approach do not afford a wide range of tools for analysis, which plummets their ability to effectively assist in policy formulation.

- **Energy System Optimization Modelling and Efficiency in Electricity Generation**

Another thread within the realm of the literature centered on the analysis of energy systems' dynamics and the exploration of methodologies aimed at enhancing electricity generating efficiency, while concurrently reducing emissions and promoting the transition to sustainable and eco-friendly energy sources. Decarolis et al. (2017) undertook a thorough review of existing literature to establish best practice for optimization modelling of energy systems. Their analysis confirmed that energy system optimization models (ESOMs) have the capability to provide accurate insights that inform national climate targets, environmental and energy policymaking, emphasizing importance of providing guidance on effective application.

Kueppers et al. (2021) recognized the importance of energy system modelling in identifying the optimal mix of technologies for the most effective carbon mitigation strategies at national level. They proposed a new method of energy system archetypes that allowed for direct evaluation and categorization of countries based on their similarities, irrespective of their geographical location, in an effort to maximize the number of countries analyzed while minimizing the modelling workload. Plazas-Niño et al. (2022) conducted a thorough examination of the main ESOMs to find patterns in scenario analyses for national economies' decarbonization pathways. Their findings revealed that ESOMs are valuable tools for developing scenarios that capture the various interactions between energy sources, end uses, and transformation technologies, and further supporting decision-making in formulating optimal decarbonization pathways.

- **Utilization of LEAP for Simulating Future Scenarios in Research Studies**

Several studies utilized LEAP to simulate futuristic scenarios of energy supply and assess their impacts on key variables, such as energy consumption, GHG emissions, and economic indicators, at country level. Huang et al. (2011) employed LEAP to simulate the future energy demand, supply, and CO₂ emissions in Taiwan. Their study analyzed several energy policy scenarios from 2008 to 2030. The findings indicated that under a business-as-usual scenario, oil refining was a primary contributor to the total energy output for 2030, followed by electricity generation. McPherson & Karney (2014) used LEAP to evaluate the present state of Panama's power production and predict how it could evolve in the future, and the impact on various factors including the potential for global warming, resource diversity, and system marginal costs. Ates (2015) used the LEAP system as a means of evaluating the capacity for enhancing energy efficiency and mitigating carbon emissions in Turkey's steel and iron sector. Emodi et al. (2017) utilized the LEAP system to examine the future energy supply and consumption and carbon emissions of Nigeria between 2010 and 2040. Mirjat et al. (2018) employed LEAP to simulate the power system of Pakistan over 2015-2050. Hu et al. (2019) developed the Shenzhen-LEAP model capitalizing on the city's post-industrial characteristics in constructing four scenarios to investigate its energy supply and demand from 2015 to 2030. Nieves et al. (2019) built a LEAP model to forecast and evaluate the energy outlook in Colombia from 2015 to 2030 and further to 2050, considering two distinct pathways in their analysis. Felver (2020) utilized LEAP to forecast Azerbaijan's potential CO₂ emissions through three distinct scenarios. Shahid et al. (2021) created a LEAP model for Pakistan's electricity system from 2016 to 2040. Furthermore, a LEAP model was developed by Yang et al. (2021) to examine the ecological and socioeconomic impact of the introduction of renewables in the Chinese province of Zhang.

- **Energy Modelling Studies with a Focus on Egypt**

Some studies utilized energy modelling to underline the importance of promoting renewables for generating electricity and fostering a green economy in Egypt. Shaaban & Scheffran (2017) developed a methodical approach in order to assess the different power supply systems in Egypt. The results of their research showed that for a meaningful long-term evaluation of the energy sector, power projects should have social and environmental considerations factored in, and not only technical and economic aspects. Rady et al. (2018) assessed the economic and environmental implications of Egypt's planned growth in the power sector using the Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OSe-MOSYS) in exploring two different energy demand scenarios. Findings revealed that wind power technology is the most appropriate choice for boosting renewables in the country's energy mix. Moreover, wind power represented a feasible alternative that could potentially reduce the dependence on natural gas in Egypt's energy sector. Mondal et al. (2019) examined Egypt's power sector energy supply strategies using the TIMES model, with a particular emphasis on CO₂ mitigation, renewables integration, and restrictions on natural gas usage. Findings of their research indicated that energy mix diversification is necessary to improve supply reliability, reduce reliance on fossil fuels, and lower GHG emissions.

Chapter Three

Climate Change & Energy in the Egyptian Context

As Egypt navigates the complexities of environmental sustainability, it faces a multitude of challenges rooted in its unique geographical and socio-economic landscape. This chapter delves into the country's environmental profile, highlighting the pressing issues of pollution, climate change, water scarcity, and land degradation that threaten its natural resources and public health. Egypt, strategically positioned at the intersection of Africa, Asia, and Europe, experiences increased population pressures, rapid urbanization, and industrial growth, intensifying these environmental dilemmas. The Nile River, a vital freshwater resource, serves as the backbone of Egypt's agriculture and economy but is increasingly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, alongside the coastal areas that face rising sea levels. Through this examination, the chapter attempts to provide an answer for one of the three sub-questions posed by the study; *“What are the drivers of climate change in Egypt, and what potential impacts do they pose?”* exploring the vulnerability of Egypt's communities to climate change, key drivers of GHG emissions across various sectors, and the critical need for sustainable practices within the energy sector for a resilient future amidst escalating environmental challenges.

3.1. Country Environmental Profile

Egypt faces immense environmental challenges associated with pollution, climate change, water scarcity, and land degradation. Rapid urbanization, escalating population growth, and industrial expansion have led to increased pressure on its dwindling resources and have exacerbated environmental issues. The country is strategically located in the northeastern corner of Africa, bordered by the Mediterranean Sea to the north and the Red Sea to the east. Geographically, it is positioned at the crossroads between Africa, Asia, and Europe, making it a bridge between the three continents. Its location within the Euro Mediterranean region is quite significant as it connects Mediterranean Sea to Red Sea, allowing for access to major international shipping routes. The country's coastal areas along the Mediterranean Sea serve as important gateways for trade with Europe, while the Suez Canal acts as a vital maritime passage for global commerce, linking the Mediterranean with the Indian Ocean (World Bank, 2021).

Known for its iconic Nile River, vast stretches of desert, and coastal areas along the Mediterranean and Red seas, Egypt's environmental profile is as dynamic as it is challenging as more than 90% of the country is covered with expansive arid and semi-arid environments making it highly susceptible to climate change impacts. This leads to limited freshwater resources and significant reliance on the Nile River for water supply. Furthermore, increased temperatures and changing precipitation patterns could negatively affect water availability from the Nile and further strain the already stressed water resources. Air pollution remains a major concern, largely due to increasing vehicular and industrial emissions. Waste management persists as a critical environmental problem in Egypt as the country struggles with waste collection and processing, resulting in uncontrolled dumping and burning of waste, leading to further air and land pollution (World Bank, 2022a).

3.2.Vulnerability to Climate Change

Climate change impacts, such as changes in rainfall patterns and increased temperatures, pose a significant risk to water availability and increase the risk of water scarcity and desertification. In recent years, climate change has had a considerable impact on the country demonstrated by rising temperatures and changing precipitation patterns which have led to an increase in the intensity and frequency of extreme weather events. These impacts also had substantial effects on vital aspects of infrastructure, coastal areas, and the fertile lands of the Nile delta, and imposed many consequences on critical sectors such as energy and industry (World Bank, 2021, 2022a).

Agriculture plays a crucial role in Egypt's economy, providing employment to many Egyptians and food security. However, changes in temperature and rainfall patterns associated with climate change can have severe consequences for agricultural productivity. Shifts in growing seasons, water availability, and pest dynamics can lead to reduced crop yields, increased food prices, and decreased income for farmers, exacerbating poverty and food insecurity (World Bank, 2021). Coastal areas are also at serious risk due to rising sea-level and increased storm surges which threatens infrastructure, human settlements, and valuable ecosystems along the coast.

The country's rapidly growing population is placing additional strain on already limited resources. With an estimated annual population growth rate of 1.6%, Egypt is projected to reach a population of 150 million by 2050. This rapid expansion exacerbates the demand for food, water, and energy, thus intensifying the pressure on ecosystems and increasing the risk of resource depletion (World Bank, 2021, 2022a, 2022b). Widespread poverty also contributes to the country's vulnerability to climate change, hinders adaptive capacity, and limits access to resources and services. Impoverished communities often lack access to basic services, tend to rely more on natural resources for their livelihoods, and have limited capacity to cope with climate-related shocks and stresses. These communities are particularly vulnerable to extreme weather events such as droughts and/or floods, which can lead to food insecurity, loss of homes and livelihoods, and increased susceptibility to diseases. Rapid urbanization in major cities, especially those along coastal areas, are experiencing rapid growth, leading to the expansion of infrastructure, industry, and human settlements and increases their exposure to climate-related hazards. Urban centers also face challenges like inadequate housing, lack of basic services, and informal settlements, which intensify their vulnerability to climate change impacts (World Bank, 2021).

3.3.Drivers of GHG Emissions

GHG emissions in Egypt span multiple sectors mainly energy, industrial processes, agriculture, and transport. These sectors are crucial to Egypt's developing economy and pose serious environmental challenges due to their significant contribution to GHG emissions.

- **Energy**

The energy sector is the most significant contributor to GHG emissions primarily due to the heavily reliance on fossil fuels where natural gas and oil account for approximately 95% of the country's total primary energy supply (MoERE, 2021b). The energy sector is also responsible for other emissions such as methane, nitrous oxide, and sulfur dioxide. This problem is exacerbated by

growing energy consumption linked to rapid urbanization, increased use of powered appliances, and a rapidly growing population (Egyptian Environmental Affairs Agency. The residential sector reigns as the predominant consumer of energy, accounting for almost half of the total power consumption. The industrial and service sectors also have substantial electricity use, further accentuating the growing demand. Climatic conditions, primarily the hot desert climate, have contributed to high electricity usage due to the increasing need for cooling during the unusually prolonged hot season (EEAA, 2018, 2022; ARE, 2023).

- **Industry**

Egypt's industrial sector, comprising manufacturing, construction, and mining, is also a major contributor to the country's GHG emissions, particularly cement production which is an energy-intensive activity that releases substantial amounts of CO₂ both from the combustion of fossil fuels and the calcination of limestone. Other segments of the industrial sector including iron, steel, and chemical production, also immensely contribute to GHG emissions (EEAA, 2018, 2022).

- **Transportation**

Transportation is also a major source of emissions in Egypt where the sector is responsible for about 6% of the country's total emissions, with cars, buses, and trucks responsible for the majority of these emissions through the burning of fossil fuels (World Bank, 2021).

- **Agriculture**

The agriculture sector and agricultural practices also add to the amount of annual GHG emissions in Egypt through several mechanisms. Rice cultivation and livestock farming are two of the biggest contributors, with the latter producing substantial amounts of methane and nitrous oxide. The process of burning agricultural residues, which is a common practice in Egypt's agricultural sector, also leads to the release of CO₂ and other potent gases in the air. Also, desertification, land-use change, soil erosion primarily driven by urbanization and unsustainable land-use practices, contribute considerably to the emissions (World Bank, 2021).

- **Population**

Egypt's population is currently undergoing a rapid expansion, with an annual growth rate of 1.6%, leading to a population estimate of 106 million people as of 2023 (World Bank, 2022b). The size of the population plays a significant role in determining annual emissions as larger populations tend to have higher energy consumption and increased resource demands, resulting in elevated amounts of emissions. This is attributed to factors such as heightened transportation usage, expanded industrial activities, and greater energy requirements in residential and commercial sectors (Mujtaba et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2022; Haouas et al., 2023).

3.4.Potential Impacts of Climate Change in Egypt

Climate change is expected to have far-reaching impacts in Egypt, including water scarcity, coastal erosion, and challenges related to rising temperatures and extreme heat events. These climate-related challenges could exacerbate existing social and economic vulnerabilities and potentially lead to increased strain on resources and services, particularly in vulnerable communities.

- **Water Supply Disruptions**

Water scarcity is one of the most pressing challenges for Egypt that is highly exacerbated by climate change. The Nile River that serves as Egypt's lifeline supplying 55.5 billion cubic meters of fresh water annually providing as such sustenance for the agricultural sector and supporting the needs of households and industrial activities. Alterations in precipitation patterns, rainfall variation, and heightened rates of evaporation because of the shifting temperatures, pose a significant risk to the river's flow as well as its hydrological system (EEAA, 2022). Additionally, given the exponential increase in population and corresponding expansion of agricultural demands, any disturbances to the water supply of the Nile can potentially result in substantial implications for food security, sustainability of livelihoods, domestic water consumption, and the overall economy. Moreover, since that agriculture in Egypt is heavily reliant on irrigation from the Nile River, with a significant portion of the population engaged in this sector, climate change can provoke higher frequency and intensity of severe weather conditions including heatwaves, storms, erratic rainfall patterns, and droughts, which affects water availability and accessibility for farming, leads to land aridity and soil degradation, harms crop yields, threatens food security, and disrupts farmers' livelihoods, perpetuating a cycle of environmental and agricultural vulnerability ((World Bank, 2021, 2022a).

- **Rising Sea-Level**

Climate change is also a main driver of rising sea-level. Egypt's northern coast, which encompasses prominent urban centers such as the city of Alexandria as well as other extensive agricultural regions, is confronted with such a hazard. Rise in sea-level also gives rise to a range of adverse effects including coastal erosion, saltwater intrusion, and heightened risk of floods. It also jeopardizes the densely inhabited coastal regions and endangers infrastructure along the coast including buildings, roads, and ports. Furthermore, changes in temperature and weather patterns can bring forth significant effects on both the Mediterranean and Red Sea conditions as well as fish habitats, resulting in alternations in fish populations, patterns of migration, and overall availability. This situation has significant implications for Egypt's fishing industry and impacts in a negative way the livelihoods of communities that depend on fisheries and seafood exports.

- **Public Health Challenges**

Climate change also poses significant impacts on public health and the health sector in Egypt. The changing climate patterns and rising temperatures contribute to various health risks, exacerbating existing health challenges and placing an increased burden on the healthcare system. One of the primary impacts of climate change on public health in Egypt is the increased occurrence of heat-related illnesses. Extreme heatwaves become more frequent and intense, leading to heat exhaustion, heatstroke, and other heat-related conditions. These illnesses can have severe consequences, especially for vulnerable populations such as the elderly, children, and individuals with pre-existing health conditions (World Bank, 2021).

Moreover, climate change influences the transmission of vector-borne diseases, rising temperatures and changing rainfall patterns affect the distribution and population dynamics of

disease-carrying mosquitoes, increasing the risk of diseases like malaria, dengue fever, and West Nile virus. These diseases pose a significant threat to public health and require proactive measures for prevention and control. Respiratory diseases are another area of concern; climate change can worsen already deteriorated air quality through factors like increased pollution and the spread of allergenic plant species, which aggravate respiratory conditions such as asthma, allergies, and other respiratory ailments.

- **Energy System Disruptions**

Climate change also has profound and wide-ranging implications for Egypt's energy sector. One of the most significant consequences of climate change is the anticipated rise in energy demand. As temperatures rise, the need for cooling services, such as air conditioning, escalates. This surge in electricity consumption for cooling purposes puts strain on the power infrastructure and can lead to blackouts or energy shortages. Additionally, heatwaves, storms, floods and other extreme weather events can damage energy infrastructure, causing power outages and disrupting the transmission and distribution of electricity. In particular, transmission lines can be susceptible to wind damage, while heavy rainfall and flooding can impact substations and power plants (World Bank, 2021, 2022a).

Climate change can also impact the availability and reliability of the renewable energy infrastructure that the country has been investing in, particularly solar and wind power. Changes in weather patterns, such as shifts in wind patterns or increased cloud cover can affect the generation potential of solar and wind farms. This variability may introduce challenges in grid management and stability and require advanced forecasting and energy storage solutions.

Moreover, water scarcity as a result of climate change also has negative impacts on the energy sector. Hydropower generated from the Aswan high dam and the other small dams located along the Nile River are put at high risk due to changes in rainfall patterns and increased evaporation due to rising temperatures, which has the ability to reduce water availability in the Nile, impacting hydropower generation. This poses challenges for meeting the country's growing energy demands and necessitates the development of alternative energy sources.

Coastal areas of Egypt, where the country's oil and gas facilities are concentrated, are vulnerable to climate change-induced coastal erosion, storm surges, and sea-level rise. These impacts pose risks to the energy infrastructure and can lead to disruptions in energy production and supply. Furthermore, global oil price fluctuations resulting from climate-related events can impact Egypt's energy security. As a net importer of oil and natural gas, the country's energy import bills are vulnerable to extreme weather events in oil-producing regions. Earthquakes and droughts in these areas can disrupt global oil markets and lead to price volatility, affecting Egypt's economy and energy affordability (IPCC, 2014).

- **Risks to Tourism Industry**

Tourism is a major economic sector in Egypt that holds significant importance, making substantial contributions to both the nation's economy and cultural heritage. With its rich history, ancient monuments and vibrant cultural experiences, Egypt offers a unique appeal to travelers from around

the world. A thriving tourism industry supports job creation, infrastructure development, and preserves the country's archaeological treasures, ensuring their preservation for future generations while promoting cross-cultural exchange and understanding.

Climate change has the potential to significantly impact Egypt's historical monuments and sites in several ways. The warming trend could lead to increased deterioration of materials from thermal stress. Materials like stone, metal, and wood, commonly found in these monuments, could expand and contract with temperature changes leading to its degradation. Shifts in local weather patterns brought about by climate change cause increased humidity and precipitation. More moisture can notably encourage growth of biological organisms (algae, lichens, fungi, etc.) that can degrade the surfaces of these monuments (Sesana et al., 2018; Downes, 2019).

Egypt's historic sites near coastal regions and Nile Delta are particularly vulnerable to rising sea-level. Saline water intrusion can lead to the deterioration of archeological remains buried within the soil. Coastal erosion represents serious threats to the country's coastal tourism destinations and notable coastal cities and resorts that attract millions of tourists every year. Severe weather events and temperature variations can negatively impact visitor comfort and preferences and result in diminished number of visitors and reduced tourism related revenues.

Climate change can also lead to changes in wind patterns and more frequent and intense sandstorms, which can erode the exposed surfaces of historical structures. Furthermore, increased levels of CO₂ in the atmosphere can cause 'stone weathering' which is a process of degradation, alteration, or erosion of stones and rocks over time, due to natural or anthropogenic factors that can occur through various mechanisms including physical, chemical, and biological processes.

Archeological sites and historic monuments undergo stone weathering through three types. The first of these types is physical weathering which is the physical breakdown of rocks due to temperature changes, water freezing, and/or expanding in cracks and abrasion from wind and rain. The second type is chemical weathering in which chemical reactions between the rock minerals and environmental elements such as water, acids, and gases lead to the dissolution, oxidation, and/or other forms of alteration. The third type is biological weathering, this type occurs when living organisms, like lichens or roots, colonize and break down the rock through their growth and activities. This explains how stone weathering can significantly impact the structural integrity and aesthetic appearance of architectural monuments, sculptures, and natural rock formation over time due to changes in climatic conditions (Oguchi & Yu, 2021).

The potential impacts of climate change on Egypt are wide-ranging and have the potential to disrupt various aspects of the country. From increased temperatures and water scarcity to coastal erosion and changes in ecosystems, Egypt faces significant challenges resulting from climate change. These impacts can have cascading effects on sectors such as agriculture, energy, tourism, and public health. Additionally, extreme weather events like heatwaves and floods can pose risks to infrastructure and human wellbeing. It is crucial that Egypt recognizes the urgency of addressing climate change and takes collective action to mitigate its potential impacts. Through implementing sustainable practices and developing adaptive strategies, Egypt can strive towards a more resilient and sustainable future in the face of climate change.

3.5.Overview of Energy Sector in Egypt

Energy is a main driver of economic development in Egypt which constitutes more than 13% of the country's overall GDP. The energy sector is considered a significant contributor to employment in Egypt and a major source of jobs for many Egyptians (Information and Decision Support Center, 2022). Moreover, energy constitutes a vital component within the comprehensive framework of Egypt's Sustainable Development Strategy, also known as Egypt's Vision 2030, which encompasses ten interconnected pillars emanating from the broader economic dimension. Anchored within this visionary strategy, the energy pillar assumes a prominent role in driving the country's transition towards a more sustainable and resilient future, incorporating ambitious goals aiming at transforming the country's energy landscape towards a low-carbon future. The energy pillar's primary objectives are boosting the renewables share in the energy mix, improving energy efficiency, and enhancing energy security (Ministry of Planning and Economic Development (MPED), 2021). In line with its broad plan for sustainable energy, Egypt aims to grow its local content by sourcing 42% of its electricity from renewables by 2030 (MoERE, 2015b; Supreme Energy Council (SEC), 2016; ARE, 2023).

3.5.1. Sources of Energy

Egypt is gifted with a plethora of different sources of energy, including natural gas, oil, hydroelectric, and a promising potential for solar and wind energy. Moreover, the country is endowed with a substantial expanse of land, characterized by a mostly sunny climate and consistently strong wind patterns, making it an optimal geographical region for the implementation of renewable energy initiatives and the market for renewable energy has the potential to generate billions of dollars in revenue (Information Trade Administration (ITA), 2022).

Electricity is a key component of Egypt's overall energy system, playing a crucial role in powering and sustaining the country's socioeconomic development. The sector primarily relies on a mix of conventional and renewable energy sources to meet the growing electricity demand, dominated by oil and gas at approximately 90%. Renewable energy sources (wind and solar) account for 5.1%, while hydropower constitutes 4.8% of the total electricity generation capacity (MoERE, 2022b).

- **Oil**

The energy sector in Egypt has traditionally been centered around the production and exportation of oil and natural gas. In terms of oil production, Egypt is the third major natural gas producer in Africa and the 25th largest in the world. The country also functions as a critical channel for oil transported from the Persian Gulf to Europe and United States (Energy Information Administration (EIA), 2022). Egypt has emerged as a frontrunner in the global petroleum industry, with significant achievements since 1886 when the country marked its entry with the drilling of the first well in the Jamsa area, situated on the western coast of the Red Sea. In 1961, the country discovered its first offshore oil field, Belayiem offshore, which was also the first in the entire Middle East region. Currently, the Western Desert dominates oil production in Egypt, accounting for the largest share at 56%, Suez Gulf at 23%, Eastern Desert at 12%, followed by Sinai at 9% (Ministry of Petroleum (MoP), 2023).

- **Natural Gas**

The Mediterranean Sea contributes the largest share of natural gas production in Egypt, accounting for 62% of the total output followed by the Nile Delta region at 19% and the Western Desert at 18%. In recent years, numerous natural gas discoveries have been made in Egypt to cater to the needs of the local market. Examples include the Nooros discovery in the Nile Delta, the North Alexandria and the West Nile Delta discoveries in the Mediterranean Sea, in addition to the Zohr gas field which is recognized as the largest natural gas find in the Mediterranean Sea and one of the largest worldwide (MoP, 2023). These assets, coupled with the existing Suez Canal and Sumed pipelines along with the country's potential for renewables, notably solar and wind energy, reflect its promising path towards a sustainable energy future, and further establish Egypt as a crucial energy hub in the region given its pivotal geographical location which positions it strategically for exportation and transit of energy (MoERE, 2022b).

- **Thermal Power**

Thermal power plants contribute a significant share to Egypt's electrical energy generation capacity. As of 2021, around 89% of Egypt's electricity generation came from thermal power plants that mainly rely on the combustion of fossil fuels, natural gas and oil, to generate electricity (Global Data, 2023). However, this heavy dependency on fossil fuels has contributed to high levels of GHG emissions, exacerbating climate change. Egypt's total GHG emissions accounted for approximately 325.515 MtCO_{2e} in 2015. The energy sector alone accounted for 64.5% of these emissions, 97% of this amount was attributed to fossil fuel combustion activities to generate electricity (EEAA, 2018).

- **Renewable Energy**

Egypt has implemented several solar energy initiatives on a smaller scale, such as the Kom Ombo PV plant, Kuraymat concentrated solar power (CSP) plant in Sharm El Shiekh, rooftop solar panel installations, and solar water heating systems, contributing to the overall sustainability efforts. Moreover, the country's strategic location along the Gulf of Suez allows for favorable wind conditions, making wind energy a viable clean energy option. In recent years, Egypt has undertaken significant steps towards addressing climate change and reducing emissions, in line with its commitment to sustainable development and the 2030 Agenda, and within the context of the Paris Agreement (MoERE, 2015b; MPED, 2016, 2021a, 2021b; ARE, 2022; EEAA, 2022). Examples of successfully implemented projects include Zaafarana and Gabal El-Zeit wind farms, contributing markedly to national renewable energy goals (MoERE, 2021a, 2022). The Benban Photovoltaic (PV) Park, one of the world's largest solar power projects, exemplifies Egypt's dedication in this area. With a total capacity of 1.5 gigawatts (GW), this project significantly contributes to the diversification of the energy mix while concurrently decreasing reliance on traditional fossil fuels and reducing GHG emissions.

- **Hydropower**

Hydroelectric power in Egypt plays a limited but notable role in the country's energy mix, with a total installed capacity of around 2.8 GW. The primary source of hydropower in Egypt is the

Aswan high dam which has the capacity to generate up to 2.1 GW of electricity. The dam harnesses the power of the Nile River to generate electricity and control flooding, and its waters are used to irrigate nearby lands, providing a vital source of water for both energy production and agriculture. In addition to the Aswan Dam, Egypt has other four smaller hydroelectric power stations located along the Nile River and its tributaries, which generate a further 700 MW of electricity (MoERE, 2021b, 2022).

3.5.2. Energy Efficiency

Energy efficiency measures have gained momentum in Egypt over the last two decades as the government continues to mitigate the costly energy subsidies, instigate energy-efficient practices, and adopt energy-saving technologies in power generation to reduce wastage and improve the energy sector's efficiency.

- **National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP)**

In 2012, Egypt started to implement a comprehensive program that outlines specific targets to improve energy efficiency across various sectors. The National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP) sets goals for energy consumption and load reduction, renewable energy integration, and the adoption of energy-efficient technologies in industry, transportation, public facilities, and buildings. Under the umbrella of this program, Egypt implemented several energy-efficiency initiatives to reduce energy consumption and promote sustainable practices across industries, encouraging them to adopt technologies that optimize energy use and minimize environmental impact (MoERE, 2012b, 2019a, 2020a, 2021a, 2022). One of such initiatives is the Industrial Modernization Center (IMC), which targets industries directly, encouraging them to adopt energy-efficient technologies, processes, and practices with the goal of optimizing energy use and reducing GHG emissions.

- **Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy Program for the Industrial Sector (EEREI)**

The Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy Program for the Industrial Sector (EEREI) has been operational for approximately a decade, fostering energy-efficient practices and promoting the integration of renewable energy sources in the industrial sector (Ministry of Trade and Industry, 2023). Within the framework of NEEAP, the Ministry of Petroleum implemented an energy subsidy reform program to align national energy prices with global prices which increased the need for energy conservation and efficiency. In 2017, the ministry implemented a program for energy efficiency, with the primary objective of enhancing these measures across petroleum sector projects (MoP, 2021).

- **Energy Efficiency in Transportation Sector**

The country has also prioritized sustainable transportation solutions. Cairo's metro system has been expanded several times to cover more areas, reducing the reliance on private vehicles. The introduction of electric buses and the establishment of dedicated cycling lanes further encourage the adoption of sustainable modes of transportation. Moreover, the country has implemented

incentives for the adoption of electric vehicles, such as subsidies and tax breaks, promoting a shift towards cleaner transportation options (MoERE, 2021a, 2022a).

3.5.3. Decarbonizing Egypt's Energy Sector: Challenges and Opportunities

The energy sector is among the sectors contributing most to global GHG emissions along with industry and transport, responsible alone for more than 75% of global emissions (IEA, 2022). Furthermore, the energy sector is the single most extensive source of energy-related CO₂ emissions globally, accounting for roughly 42% of total global energy-related emissions (UNEP, 2022). Climate change requires strategic and innovative actions from all sectors of an economy, the energy sector, due to its significant contribution to GHG emissions, holds a critical role in mitigating climate change and transitioning to a sustainable and low-carbon future. Addressing climate change demands a pledge from the energy sector towards decarbonization, this involves incorporating it into energy planning processes, the protection of existing power generation facilities from extreme weather events and planning future facilities taking into account the potential impacts of climate change (Cronin et al., 2018; Adeleye et al., 2021).

Over the past decade, Egypt's increasing population and aspiring economic prospects have created a surging demand for energy, coupled with rapid urbanization and industrialization, extending to electricity usage. The residential sector reigns as the predominant consumer of energy, accounting for almost half of the total power consumption. The industrial and service sectors also have substantial electricity use, further accentuating the growing demand. Climatic conditions, primarily the hot desert climate, have contributed to high electricity usage due to the increasing need for cooling during the unusually prolonged hot season (EEAA, 2022; ARE, 2023).

Renewable energy can immensely contribute to Egypt's energy security, as well as stimulate the economy through the thousands of jobs these projects can create, and even improve public health by reducing emissions and air pollution. Renewables are also advantageous in terms of long-term cost-effectiveness as the prices of solar, wind, and other green technologies become cheaper with long-term usage. Furthermore, the costs for installing such technologies have also been declining remarkably in recent years, making them more affordable and an appealing clean choice when compared to traditional fossil fuels (World Bank, 2022a).

Energy efficiency is a critical component of any decarbonization strategy. By improving energy efficiency, countries can reduce their energy needs and decrease reliance on fossil fuels. Energy-saving appliances, efficient lighting, and insulation of buildings all contribute to increased energy efficiency. Such interventions, when widely adopted, can have transformational effects on Egypt's energy consumption patterns. Moreover, they can help curb the emissions from the residential and commercial sectors, bringing about significant decreases in the nation's overall emission levels. Also, by improving energy efficiency, households and industries can significantly reduce not only their consumption of electricity, but also energy costs (World Economic Forum, 2023; IEA, 2023). Furthermore, nuclear energy offers an opportunity and a promising pathway to decarbonize the country's energy system since that nuclear power plants can generate electricity without emitting CO₂, making them an attractive low-carbon option to complement renewables, particularly given their ability to provide consistent energy regardless of weather conditions.

Egypt is currently constructing its first nuclear plant on the Mediterranean coast. The primary objectives of this project are enhancing energy security, reducing carbon emissions, fostering sustainable development, diversifying its energy portfolio, and decreasing reliance on fossil fuels, which would significantly boost the country's energy generation capacity when completed (SEC, 2016; Nuclear Power Plants Authority, 2023). However, while the transition to renewable energy presents numerous benefits, there are also challenges to be taken into consideration. For instance, the intermittent nature of solar and wind power requires substantial investment in storage systems and grid infrastructure to ensure reliability. Additionally, scaling up renewable technologies can often meet with bureaucratic hurdles and requires significant upfront capital. Meeting these challenges requires supportive policy frameworks, efficient administrative processes, and innovative financing mechanisms. Also, it is crucial to address the risks related to social acceptance and the potential displacement of jobs in fossil fuel-based industries.

In conclusion, decarbonizing the energy sector in Egypt is a complex task, but it offers immense opportunities and benefits from both an economic and environmental perspectives. Transitioning to renewables, promoting energy efficiency, and considering low-carbon alternatives like nuclear energy will be key ingredients of successful decarbonization efforts. However, surmounting the challenges involved will require strong policy commitment, significant investment, and robust stakeholder involvement, with them all aimed at a sustainable and green future in Egypt.

Chapter Four

Empirical Analysis

4.1. Methodology

This study aims to analyze and identify optimal pathways that facilitate a seamless energy transition from reliance on fossil fuels to cleaner energy alternatives in Egypt, all while ensuring the fulfillment of the country's energy future demand necessary for its expansion plans for economic growth. To achieve this aim, the study employs both quantitative and qualitative approaches along with a modelling framework, namely the Long-range Energy Alternatives Planning system (LEAP), to simulate the country's energy demand and supply from 2010 to 2050. In the following sections, the materials and methods used to analyze data, sources of data, alongside scenario design and analysis are described in more detail.

4.1.1. Materials and Methods

The study used the Long-range Energy Alternatives Planning system (LEAP) created by the Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI). LEAP is an energy-economic modelling tool with the ability to perform scenario-based modelling of the energy sector using top-down, bottom-up, and integrated approaches. It is widely used for energy policy analysis and assessing measures for climate change mitigation. It can also support capacity expansion planning at the macro-economic level over the medium to longer terms up to fifty-years forecast period. The system is not specifically designed to model a particular energy system, but it is a flexible tool that can be customized to generate models for a variety of energy systems, each with its own dataset (SEI, 2020). The system has the capability to support diverse modelling approaches on the demand side, ranging from detailed bottom-up calculation methods for end-use consumption to top-down macroeconomic modelling. On supply side, it can provide an array of modelling and optimization approaches that have the capacity to accurately simulate energy production and capacity development plans within the energy sector. Figure 1 illustrates calculations flow in LEAP.

Figure 1: Structure of LEAP Calculations Flow. Source: SEI (2020)

The system operates on two primary levels of conceptualization. The system's inherent calculators automatically handle the "non-controversial" energy, emissions, and cost-benefit computations. Users can further adjust system settings according to their own needs and lodge their own data into system's framework at second level, and integrate econometric and simulation methodologies into the system's accounting framework by inputting expressions. The optimization modelling capability of the system remains applicable even in scenarios where constraints such as limits on GHG emissions and air pollution are present.

4.1.2. Algorithm of LEAP

In this section, the computational framework for analyzing and predicting output data in LEAP is presented, including the calculations of energy consumption, transformation, emissions, and energy generation costs.

- **Consumption**

The calculations of the final energy consumption and net consumption for transformation are performed as described below (Feng & Zhang, 2012):

$$EC_n = \sum_i \sum_j AL_{n,j,i} \times EI_{n,j,i} \quad (1)$$

Where EC_n stands for the total energy consumption in a given sector, AL represents the activity level, EI indicates the energy intensity, n denotes the primary energy source, i represents the sector, and j is the technology being utilized.

$$ET_s = \sum_m \sum_t ETP_{t,m,s} \times \left(\frac{1}{f_{t,m,s}} - 1 \right) \quad (2)$$

Where ET_s represents the net energy consumption associated with the process of transformation. ETP is the resulting energy transformation product. f denotes the efficiency of transformation, s is primary energy source, m represents technology used, and t is energy produced.

- **Transformation**

Primary energy is converted to secondary energy in the transformation module. As well, this involves the conversion of electricity transmission and distribution (T&D) centers, power plants, oil refineries, coal mining, and other processes (Lazarus et al., 1997). Hence, for every process p ;

$$INPUT_p = \frac{OUTPUT_p}{EFFICIENCY_p} \quad (3)$$

For the T&D module;

$$EFFICIENCY_p = 1 - \frac{LOSSES_p}{INPUT_p} \quad (4)$$

Where $INPUT$ refers to the fuel/feedstock used in a given energy system, $OUTPUT$ represents electrical energy generated, $EFFICIENCY$ denotes power plants facilities' efficacy in converting input resources into output.

- **GHG Emissions**

Outlined below is the method used to compute GHG emissions derived from final energy consumption and energy transformation, respectively (Feng & Zhang, 2012):

$$GHG_c = \sum_i \sum_j \sum_n AL_{n,j,i} \times EI_{n,j,i} \times EF_{n,j,i} \quad (5)$$

Where GHG_c represents the emissions from final energy consumption, AL denotes activity level, EI refers to the energy intensity, and EF represents the emission factor of fuel type n and technology j used in sector i .

$$GHG_T = \sum_s \sum_m \sum_t ETP_{t,m} \times \frac{1}{f_{t,m,s}} \times EF_{t,m,s} \quad (6)$$

Where GHG_T represents emissions from energy transformation, ETP is transformation product, f represents transformation efficiency. EF is the emissions per unit of primary fuel s to generate secondary fuel t using technology m .

- **Generation Costs**

The following equation is used to calculate the total cost of a given sector (Emodi et al., 2017):

$$C = \sum_i \sum_j \left\{ \left[\sum_n \left(e_{n,j,k} \cdot ep_n \right) + \sum_k \left(m_{k,j,i} \cdot mp_k \right) + fc_{j,i} \right] P_{j,i} \right\} \quad (7)$$

Where C denotes total cost, ep represents the price of one unit of fuel n , m introduces raw material demand k per unit of production by technology j in production process i , mp refers to unit price for material k , fc is fixed cost incurred/unit production via technology j in process i .

4.1.3. Scenario Development

- **LEAP Framework for Egypt**

This section presents an overview of the LEAP analysis framework for Egypt. In the base year, the model incorporates historical energy demand data for the country's various energy consumer sectors, including residential, commercial, agricultural, utilities, industry, governmental institutions, public illumination and exports, with energy costs established for each of these sectors. An in-depth energy analysis starts with examining energy demand as it forms the basis for resource energy and transformation analyses, relying on the findings of energy demand analysis. Once energy demand analysis was established, the LEAP model proceeds to examine the available energy supply resources and transformation technologies. The transformation analysis component focuses on managing technological approaches for converting different sources of energy including fossil fuels, hydropower, wind and solar energy, and nuclear energy into electrical power. This conversion process takes into consideration the existing and projected facilities accessible throughout the study period. Performance parameters for all technologies were provided including plant capacity, capacity credit, efficiency, availability, historical output, fuel used, T&D losses, dispatch rule, load curve and reserve margin (SEI, 2005).

The following step in the modelling process is resource analysis involving collecting data pertaining to primary resources, including traditional and non-traditional sources of energy. For the specific purpose of this study, the analysis considered factors such as domestic production costs, import and export dynamics of primary sources, and secondary fuels (electricity). The environmental impact of the different technologies and emissions associated with fossil fuels were also assessed during this stage. The model then generates its output by means of two sequential analytical phases of calculation and optimization. In the accounting stage, based on the input data provided, the model calculates the projected energy consumption for all sectors during the simulation period by identifying the overall energy needed to fulfill the increasing energy demand without integrating capacities associated with the various technologies. The final stage of the analysis is optimization with cost-benefit analysis and environmental loadings factored-in. The system determines the most economically-efficient approach for expanding capacity and allocating supply-side transformation modules through utilizing linear programming-based frameworks considering all costs and benefits involved in the system, including costs pertaining to technology investment, decommissioning expenses, operation and maintenance, fuel prices, and assessment of environmental externalities. Following optimization, the primary outputs are produced including each technology's optimized capacity, energy produced per primary source, overall cost of production, and anticipated emissions (SEI, 2021). Figure 2 illustrates the framework of LEAP analysis for Egypt.

- **Scenario Design and Analysis**

The development of the LEAP model for Egypt took into account the year 2010 as its baseline year and 2050 as end year of analysis. Four alternative energy production scenarios were examined with the aim of identifying the optimal energy mix scenario for Egypt. The business-as-usual scenario (BAS) serves as the baseline for the model covering the period from 2010 to 2021, developed in LEAP system to align with current national plans for the fuel mix used in electricity generation. The underlying theory behind the development of the other four scenarios, despite having the same power generation capacity as BAS, involves the phased retirement of traditional energy production plants. These plants would be replaced by technologies introduced in these scenarios such as renewables (wind and solar), hydropower, nuclear, with the objective of maximizing the capacity of each of these technologies by expanding their deployment as much as possible. The proposed scenarios are then compared and evaluated by the LEAP system based on their individual economic costs and benefits, energy requirements, and carbon footprint.

- **Proposed Scenarios**

A comprehensive analysis was conducted to evaluate four energy alternative pathways with the aim of identifying the most suitable energy mix to meet Egypt's growing energy demand. The business-as-usual scenario (BAS) is used as the foundational framework for the model spanning over 2010 – 2021. The reference scenario RS1, replicates the conditions of BAS until 2050. The reference scenario RS2, models the dynamics of energy demand and supply of BAS taking into account a yearly growth rate of 5% in energy consumption from 2022 through 2050, peak annual

Figure 2: LEAP Framework for Egypt. Source: MoERE Annual Reports and LEAP System

increase in energy demand between 2005 and 2015 (MoERE, 2022a), and integrates nuclear energy into the energy mix. The study analyzed two more scenarios, RE1 and RE2, that aim to promote the renewables' share in the overall mix to 42 and 75% by 2030 and 2050, respectively. Table 1 outlines all scenarios examined as part of this analysis.

4.2. Results and Discussion

The primary objective of this research is to address the main research question: *“What energy supply scenarios with the lowest potential for greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions best meet Egypt’s future energy demand?”* This section also answers one of the three sub-questions posed by the study: *“How does the integration of renewable energy sources into the current energy mix influence GHG emissions trends compared to scenarios that rely on fossil fuels?”* The following paragraphs present the research findings that contribute to answering the aforementioned questions, offering a comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the results obtained and providing valuable insights for energy planning and policy development in Egypt.

4.2.1. Supply

4.2.1.1. Reference Scenario – RS1

According to the LEAP model's projections, combined-cycle plants are anticipated to remain the primary technology due to the increasing energy demand. Consequently, their capacity is projected to rise from 28.36 GW in 2022 to 71.47 GW by 2050. Conversely, the growth in capacity for steam turbine plants is projected to be limited, reaching a maximum of 31.66 GW by 2050. This is attributed to the lower efficiency and higher cost of steam turbine plants compared to combined-cycle plants. On the other hand, the model indicated notable growth in the capacities of wind and solar PV plants, reaching around 40 GW and 26.05 GW, respectively, by 2050. However, the capacity of Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) plants, even though demonstrating considerable level of capacity credit and availability, is projected to reach a modest maximum of 4.17 GW by 2050 attributed to their relatively higher costs compared to conventional and renewable technologies. Furthermore, the model anticipated no further hydropower capacity attributed to the historical

Table 1: Summary of Proposed Scenarios

Scenario	Description	Demand	Supply	Nuclear Constraint	Emission Constraint	Renewables Constraint
Business-as-Usual (BAS)	The model's baseline scenario reflecting energy developments over the years 2010 to 2021. It aligns with the current national plans for the fuel mix used in electricity generation, and provides a reference for comparison.	A substantial growth in energy demand took place over this period, particularly in the residential, industrial, and commercial sectors, with the residential sector as the largest consumer accounting solely for 40% of total demand in 2010. Increases were also observed in the agriculture, utilities, governmental sectors over this period.	Egypt experienced significant growth in its energy supply driven by a rise in energy demand. The primary sources of energy were fossil fuels such as natural gas, diesel, and heavy oil. Natural gas played a crucial role as the primary fuel for thermal plants accounting for almost 78% of the fossil fuel mix in 2010 reaching up to 95% in 2021. Renewables including hydro, wind, and solar also showed an increase in their contribution to energy supply over the same period. The main technologies for energy generation included combined cycle, steam and gas turbine plants.	No nuclear constraint	No emission constraint	No renewables constraint
Reference scenario (RS1)	This scenario replicates the change patterns of energy demand and supply in BAS until 2050.	Same as BAS	Same as BAS	No nuclear constraint	No emission constraint	No renewables constraint
Reference scenario (RS2)	Simulates energy demand and supply considering a 5% rise in demand (the peak annual increase in energy demand between 2005 and 2015 (MoERE, 2022a), integration of a new technology into the fuel mix over the period of simulation from 2022 to 2050.	An annual growth rate of 5% is applied to the average increase in energy demand.	Replicates BAS conditions while incorporating nuclear energy sources into the energy mix.	3% of energy generated shall be sourced from nuclear energy sources by 2035.	No emission constraint	No renewables constraint
Renewables-promotion (RE1)	Characterized by an increase in the share of renewables in the energy mix and imposing an emission constraint on total energy generated.	Same as RS2	Replicates RS2 conditions while increasing the share of renewables in the energy mix.	Same as RS2	37% of GHG emissions shall be reduced from electricity sector by 2030	42% of total energy production shall be sourced from renewables by 2030.
Renewables-promotion (RE2)	Characterized by a further increase in the share of renewables in the energy mix from 2022 to 2050.	Same as RS2	Replicates RS2 conditions while incrementally increasing the share of renewables and nuclear capacities in the energy mix.	Same as RS2	No emissions constraint	75% of total energy production shall be sourced from renewables by 2050.

limited capacity of hydroelectricity observed during the period of the baseline scenario. Figure 3 illustrates the projected installed capacity in the RS1 scenario categorized by generation type.

Figure 3: Installed Generation Capacity by Generation Type in RS1 Scenario

Figure 4: Expected Energy Generation by Fuel Type in RS1 Scenario

The model predicted a continued reliance on fossil fuels, particularly natural gas, which is expected to significantly rise from 147.88 TWh in 2022 to 455.73 TWh by 2050, comprising 60.42% of total primary energy. The contribution of diesel is also expected to rise from 0.86 TWh in 2022 to 3.96 TWh by 2050. The model predicted that wind energy is going to grow from 3.95 TWh in 2022 to 156.97 TWh by 2050, while solar energy is anticipated to expand from 2.97 to 99.18 TWh within the same period. The lower share of solar energy compared to wind energy can be attributed to its lower capacity credit, primarily due to PV technology. Hydro electricity is anticipated to maintain a relatively steady level of generation, with a consistent amount of 22.47 TWh until 2050 (Abdelmeguid & Ibrahiem, 2025). Figure 4 presents energy generation by fuel type for RS1.

4.2.1.2. Reference Scenario – RS2

According to the model's projections, combined-cycle plants capacity is anticipated to reach 28.50 GW in 2022 and 61.44 GW in 2050. However, there will not be a significant capacity increase between 2022 and 2035 due to limitations imposed by the nuclear constraint, which will also stabilize the capacity of steam turbine plants until 2035. Nevertheless, by 2050, this capacity is projected to witness some growth, reaching 33.56 GW. In this specific scenario, the LEAP model predicted that there would be no further increase in nuclear capacity until 2050, apart from the planned 4.8 GW, primarily due to the high investment cost associated with nuclear power. The capacities of renewable energy technologies are anticipated to exhibit a similar trend to that in the RS1 scenario, where the model projected a tangible growth in the capacities of wind and solar PV plants, with wind capacity reaching 39.24 GW and solar PV capacity reaching 28.67 GW by 2050. No foreseen increase in hydropower capacity was detected in this scenario, however, CSP capacity is forecasted to experience a mild increase reaching 4.24 GW by 2050 (Abdelmeguid & Ibrahiem, 2025). Figure 5 illustrates installed capacity by generation type in the RS2 scenario.

Figure 5: Expected Installed Generation Capacity by Generation Type in RS2 Scenario

Figure 6: Expected Energy Generation by Fuel Type in RS2 Scenario

The amount of energy from natural gas is expected to reach 147.89 TWh in 2022 and 330.25 TWh in 2050, making up 53.75% of primary energy sources by 2050. Energy generation from diesel fuel is also projected to increase from 0.86 TWh to 3.76 TWh. Due to a nuclear constraint imposed on energy production in this scenario, nuclear energy is expected to contribute 24.09 TWh to electricity generation by 2050. A foreseeable increase in wind energy was also predicted, with generation expected to rise from 3.95 TWh in 2022 to 155.36 TWh by 2050. PV energy is anticipated to significantly grow from 2.97 TWh in 2022 reaching 98.63 TWh in 2050 (Abdelmeguid & Ibrahiem, 2025). Figure 6 represents energy generation by fuel type for RS2.

4.2.1.3. Renewables-promotion Scenario – RE1

In the renewables-promotion scenario RE1, the model did not predict a substantial capacity growth for combined-cycle plants over 2022-2030. However, by 2050, CSP capacity is projected to reach 65.33 GW in response to the increasing energy demand. Additionally, the capacity of steam turbine plants is projected to reach 33.67 GW by 2050. To achieve the renewables target pertaining to this energy pathway, a substantial increase in renewable technologies is projected to occur, particularly from 2022 to 2030. As a result, the capacity of wind power plants is expected to rapidly reach 11.73 GW by 2030 compared to 1.3 GW in 2022, and further expand to 45.24 GW by 2050. Additionally, the model indicated a foreseen greater reliance on PV technology to fulfill the specified renewables target, therefore reach 14.47 GW by 2030 and eventually rise to 33.76 GW by 2050. Notably, the model forecasted no dependence on CSP, primarily due to high deployment costs compared with wind and solar PV technologies (Abdelmeguid & Ibrahiem, 2025). Figure 7 (a) illustrates expected installed capacity by generation type in the RE1 scenario, while Figure 8 (a) shows the distribution of energy generation by fuel type for the RE1 scenario.

Natural gas contribution to energy production is anticipated to decrease from 147.89 TWh in 2022 reaching 129.36 TWh in 2030, due to the introduction of renewable and nuclear capacities between 2022 and 2035. However, the model predicted a resurgence in natural gas generation by 2050 where it would reach 368.83 TWh. Natural gas is anticipated to hit its lowest point by 2045, followed by a slight increase to its peak by 2050. Furthermore, the model predicted a decline in the contribution of diesel until reaching its lowest point of 0.29 TWh by 2050. On the other hand, there is a projected significant growth in the contribution of solar and wind sources. Wind energy

is anticipated to reach 3.89 TWh in 2022 but 86.42 TWh by 2030, and ascend further to 190.33 TWh in 2050. Similarly, PV is predicted to rise from 2.86 TWh in 2022 to 28.40 TWh by 2030, and expand to 127.91 TWh by 2050. The significance of the roles played by nuclear and hydro technologies is anticipated to mirror those in the RS2 scenario (Abdelmeguid & Ibrahim, 2025).

Figure 7: Expected Installed Generation Capacity by Generation Type in RE1 (a) and RE2 (b) Scenarios

4.2.1.4. Renewables-promotion Scenario – RE2

In the RE2 scenario, designed to promote renewables, the capacity of combined-cycle plants is projected to reach 28.34 GW in 2022 and 62.29 GW in 2050. Furthermore, steam turbine plants capacity is anticipated to grow from 2.09 GW in 2022 reaching 31.74 GW in 2050. A stricter renewables constraint is implemented, wind and solar PV capacity were automatically adjusted to accommodate this objective. The projected capacity of wind plants as such is anticipated to increase from 1.3 GW in 2022 to 22.59 GW by 2030, and further rise to 50.26 GW by 2050 to meet the renewables target. Similarly, PV plants capacity is also expected to grow to 17.84 GW by 2030, and further increase to 37.65 GW by 2050. Capacities from other technologies were considered, despite their relatively higher costs, to meet set renewables target. Therefore, it is expected that CSP capacity would rise from 0.28 GW in 2022 to 5.01 GW in 2030, and 9.91 GW by 2050. Figure 7 (b) illustrates expected installed capacity by generation type in the RE2 scenario, while Figure 8 (b) shows the distribution of energy generation by fuel type for RE2.

Figure 8: Expected Energy Supply by Fuel Type in RE1 (a) and RE2 (b) Scenarios

There is a projected gradual decrease in energy generation from natural gas, persisting until it reaches its minimum level of 88.47 in 2045. Nevertheless, it is anticipated to rise again reaching 186.33 TWh by 2050, which accounts for one fourth of the overall energy generated. However, despite this increase, it is projected to remain considerably lower compared to other scenarios. In terms of energy generation from diesel, there is an observed gradual decline towards 2050 at 0.81 TWh. Wind energy is predicted to dominate the energy mix by 2050 at 298.73 TWh, starting at 3.89 TWh in 2022. After wind energy, solar energy is anticipated to have the second-largest contribution, with its generation increasing from 2.86 TWh in 2022 to 205.30 TWh by 2050. No changes are expected for nuclear and hydropower contribution (Abdelmeguid & Ibrahiem, 2025).

4.2.2. GHG Emissions

In the reference scenario RS1, the model's projections indicated that GHG emissions are expected to peak and potentially reach maxima of 389.25 MtCO_{2e} in 2030 and 493.56 MtCO_{2e} in 2050. This is predominantly attributed to the extensive dependence on fossil fuels for the generation of energy in this particular scenario, coupled with the absence of constraints on renewables, nuclear, and emission. In contrast, in RS2, GHG emissions will peak at 339.26 MtCO_{2e} in 2030 and 441.36 MtCO_{2e} in 2050. This decrease in emissions, opposed to RS1, is a result of the integration of a nuclear capacity (3%) into the energy mix starting 2035, which helps mitigate emissions to some extent but is counterbalanced by the surge in energy demand, leading to a greater reliance on fossil fuels. In the renewables-promotion scenario RE1, the model projected a modest reduction in GHG emissions compared to the RS2 scenario until 2030, where GHG emissions are estimated to reach 313.91 MtCO_{2e}. This prudent decrease is largely attributed to the increase in energy demand throughout the simulation period from 2022 to 2050, despite constraints on renewables as well as GHG emissions in the electricity sector already implemented. Yet, these factors would have a more noticeable impact in the long term in reducing GHG emissions which is expected to reach 148.21 MtCO_{2e} by 2050. The model predicted the lowest levels of GHG emissions in the renewables-promotion scenario RE2. Specifically, the model anticipated a significant decline in emissions from 120.45 MtCO_{2e} in 2030 to 53.40 MtCO_{2e} in 2050. This significant decrease in emissions is primarily attributed to implementing higher renewables target by 2050 alongside the implementation of nuclear capacity (Abdelmeguid & Ibrahiem, 2025).

4.2.3. Generation Costs

Based on the model's projections, production costs for the RS1 scenario shall rise from 5.27 to 5.88 cent/kWh in 2022 and 2050, respectively. This upward trend is mainly attributed to the ongoing increase in the cost of fossil fuels. In the RS2 scenario, the model's projections indicated that production costs will leap from 5.26 cent/kWh in 2022 to 6.05 cent/kWh in 2035. This increase can be attributed to the incorporation of more expensive nuclear technology during this period. Furthermore, the projected cost is expected to rise again to 6.20 cent/kWh by 2050. This increase is primarily driven by higher energy demand during that time, necessitating the addition of more fossil fuel capacities and resulting in increased fossil fuel expenses due to emission constraints. The adoption of modern green technologies for electricity generation also contributes to the rise

in production costs. In the RE1 scenario, the model forecasted a rise in production costs from 5.22 cent/kWh in 2022 reaching 5.88 cent/kWh in 2030. This increase can be attributed to the introduction of more renewable and nuclear capacities, as well as the implementation of an emission constraint on electricity generation, resulting in higher production costs. However, after 2030, production costs are expected to decrease to 5.62 cent/kWh in 2040. This decrease is primarily due to an increased reliance on renewable energy technologies, which have lower operational costs compared to traditional technologies. However, cost is anticipated to increase once again to 5.86 cent/kWh by 2050, driven by higher energy demand, which leads to inclusion additional fossil technologies. The model forecasted the highest production costs in the RE2 scenario between 2022 and 2030, as the cost is expected to mount to 6.44 cent/kWh in 2030, compared to 5.27 cent/kWh in 2022, due to the integration of additional renewables capacities. However, costs shall gradually decline and become lowest among all scenarios in 2050 at 5.11 cent/kWh. This reduction is attributed to the utilization of higher renewables capacities of lower long-term operational costs.

Conclusion and Policy Implications

Research findings showed that in the Reference scenario RS1, the model predicted that natural gas is expected to make the greatest contribution in comparison to other scenarios, with a share of 60.42% by 2050. This particular scenario demonstrated the most significant GHG emissions among all proposed scenarios. Although RS1 initially showed a lower production cost compared to other scenarios until 2030, the model predicted that these costs will eventually surpass energy generation costs associated with the renewable-promotion scenarios RE1 and RE2 in the long-term. So, it is not recommended for policymakers to pursue this scenario owing to its low emissions reduction potential. Moreover, RS1 does not offer an optimal diversification of the energy mix portfolio. Despite its initially cost-effective nature, from a long-term economic perspective, this pathway is not seen as a viable choice.

Reference scenario RS2, which incorporated a constraint on nuclear technology, demonstrated potential in boosting energy security in future through reducing the share of natural gas down to 53.8% by 2050, while nuclear energy was expected to contribute up to 24.09 TWh to electricity generation, thereby maintaining a 5% share of the overall energy production. The implementation of the nuclear constraint, when compared to RS1, contributed to reducing additional emissions by 2050. The projected energy production costs in this scenario are expected to be the highest among all scenarios, rising from 5.26 cent/kWh in 2022 reaching 6.05 cent/kWh in 2035 and 6.20 cent/kWh in 2050. This increase can be attributed to incorporation of costlier nuclear technology during this period.

The second rise is primarily driven by higher energy demand between 2036 and 2050, which necessitated the addition of more fossil capacities leading to increased expenses due to the emission constraint. The adoption of modern green technologies for electricity generation also contributed to the increase in production costs. Policymakers are advised to prioritize achieving a balanced and diversified energy mix. This would reduce reliance on a single energy source and increases resilience in the face of fluctuating energy prices and supply disruptions. The deployment of renewables can effectively reduce emissions, promote environmental sustainability, and capitalize on innovations in clean energy technologies.

Both RE1 and RE2 scenarios are expected to have the lowest GHG emissions by 2050, with 148.21 MtCO_{2e} and 53.40 MtCO_{2e}, respectively. Although the cost of energy production may go up when more renewables capacity is introduced at once, it is expected that this price hike would be short-lived one as generation costs tend to drop with time. RE2 is expected to have the lowest production cost among all scenarios by 2050, with a predicted minimum of 5.11 cent/kWh. Given that production costs are projected to rise to a high of 5.88 cent/kWh and 6.20 cent/kWh for the RS1 and RS2 by 2050, switching to renewables not only has environmental and security advantages, but also establishes a favorable investment atmosphere, and boosts the economy in the long run. However, one of the primary challenges that may hinder their implementation is the economic viability of renewable energy. This is due to small capacity credit associated with renewable technologies, indicating their relatively limited availability compared to conventional

technologies. Hence, improving the capacity credit of renewable energy technologies will directly influence their economic viability. It is recommended therefore that policymakers implement supportive policies and incentives to encourage renewables deployment including tax credits, feed-in tariffs, and renewable portfolio obligations. Additionally, they should focus on strengthening renewable energy infrastructure by investing in transmission lines and smart grid technologies. This would reinforce renewables integration into the existing power grid and enhance energy resilience. innovation in renewable technologies, and investment in energy storage solutions to overcome intermittent generation challenges. The capacity credit of renewable energy technologies can also be improved through innovation in renewable technologies and investment in energy storage solutions to overcome intermittent generation challenges.

Moreover, in circumstances where there is an increase in investment costs due to a rise in the discount rate, conventional technologies tend to become more favorable. To mitigate costs, policymakers should strive to keep interest rates at their minimum levels and ensure the discount rate remains below 15%. Policymakers should also consider gradually phasing out subsidies on gas supply to the energy industry as well as heavy industries, which can create a significant opportunity for increased investments in renewable energy, making it more economically viable. Policymakers should also carefully balance emissions reduction targets with energy security considerations, for instance, the integration of nuclear energy, while imposing a constraint, can contribute to energy security by reducing reliance on natural gas.

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عنوان الرسالة : سيناريوهات التخطيط البديل لتقليل الانبعاثات الدفينة من قطاع الطاقة: تطبيق نموذج LEAP على قطاع

الطاقة فى مصر

المخلص

فى عام ٢٠٢٣، أكدت مصر التزامها باتفاق باريس من خلال تقديم تحديثاتها الوطنية إلى إطار الأمم المتحدة للتغير المناخي و التى تمثلت فى خطة استراتيجية مدتها خمسة عشر عامًا تمتد من عام ٢٠١٥ إلى عام ٢٠٣٠ بهدف الحد من انبعاثات غازات الاحتباس الحرارى فى الانبعاثات بنسبة ٣٧% الكهرباء (الإنتاج والنقل والتوزيع)، ٦٥% من قطاع النفط والغاز، و ٧% من قطاع النقل، مقارنة بمستويات عام ٢٠١٥. لكنه من المرجح أن تواجه آمال التوسع الاقتصادي للبلاد والزيادة المتوقعة فى استهلاك الطاقة من أجل تحقيق هذه الأهداف عدة تحديات، لاسيما فى قطاع الطاقة. تم إجراء هذه الدراسة بهدف إيجاد الحلول اللازمة لمواجهة تلك التحديات والوصول إلى انتقال طاقي سلس من الوقود الأحفوري إلى بدائل الطاقة النظيفة وتحقيق مزيج طاقي متوازن فى مصر مع ضمان استمرار النمو الاقتصادي.

تتقسم الرسالة إلى أربعة فصول، يعرض الفصل الأول أهم التعريفات والمصطلحات المستخدمة لتعميق معرفتنا بظاهرة تغير المناخ بالإضافة إلى أهم النظريات العلمية التى حاولت تفسير تلك الظاهرة. يوضح الفصل الثانى كيف يمكن تفسير ظاهرة تغير المناخ من منظور اقتصادى، يليه استعراض شامل للأدبيات و الدراسات السابقة التى تناولت الموضوع. يستكشف الفصل الثالث بشكل اعمق ظاهرة تغير المناخ داخل السياق المصرى، يليه نظرة عامة على قطاع الطاقة فى مصر بما فى ذلك التحديات و الفرص المتاحة والدور البارز الذى يلعبه القطاع كمساهم رئيسى فى انبعاثات غازات الاحتباس الحرارى فى مصر. يتناول الفصل الرابع منهجية الدراسة والمواد والأساليب المستخدمة و كذلك النتائج وتحليل البيانات و تفسيرها. تختتم الدراسة بتلخيص النتائج الرئيسية و أثر الدراسة ومساهماتها فى تحسين فهمنا للخيارات الطاقية المختلفة المتاحة و توصيات لسياسات طاقية أفضل.

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اصدار/ تعديل (0/2)

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اسم الطالب: نقيين صفوت أمين عبدالمجيد
الدرجة: الدكتوراة فى الدراسات الأوروبية المتوسطة

المستخلص

تهدف هذه الدراسة إلى تحديد سيناريوهات مزيج الطاقة ذات التكلفة الاقتصادية الأدنى التى تلبى الطلب المتزايد على الطاقة فى مصر و المساهمة الأقل فى تزايد ظاهرة الاحتباس الحرارى العالمى، والتى تساعد فى تحقيق الانتقال من الاعتماد على الوقود الأحفورى نحو مصادر طاقة مستدامة. استخدمت الدراسة منهج النمذجة (modelling) ، و بالتحديد نظام تخطيط بدائل الطاقة على المدى البعيد (LEAP)، لمحاكاة الطلب والعرض الطاقى فى مصر فى الفترة ما بين عام ٢٠١٠ إلى عام ٢٠٥٠، حيث تم تحليل اربعة سيناريوهات محتملة الى جانب سيناريو مزيج الطاقة المعتاد (BAU) Business-as-Usual. يقوم السيناريو المرجعى الأول (RS1) بتكرار أنماط تغيير الطلب على الطاقة بين عامى ٢٠١٠ و ٢٠٢٢، و حتى عام ٢٠٥٠ دون اجراء أى تغييرات على انماط السيناريو المعتاد بينما يأخذ السيناريو المرجعى الثانى (RS2) فى الاعتبار زيادة الطلب على الطاقة بنسبة ٥٪ سنويًا خلال فترة المحاكاة ما بين عامى ٢٠٢٢ و ٢٠٥٠. بالإضافة إلى سيناريوهين آخرين لتعزيز الطاقة المتجددة (RE1) و (RE2) حيث تسهم الطاقة المتجددة بنسبة ٤٢ و ٧٥٪ من اجمالى مزيج الطاقة بحلول ٢٠٣٠ و ٢٠٥٠ بالترتيب. تشير نتائج البحث الى ان الانبعاثات الدفيئة و التى تعد سببا رئيسا فى حدوث ظاهرة تغيير المناخ سوف تصل الى ذروتها فى السيناريو المرجعى الأول RS1 بينما تكون فى ادنى مستوياتها فى سيناريو تعزيز الطاقة المتجددة الثانى RE2 فى نفس النطاق الزمنى بحلول ٢٠٥٠. بينت النتائج ايضا ان تكاليف توليد الطاقة ستكون الاعلى فى السيناريو المرجعى الثانى RS2 بحلول ٢٠٥٠ و فى سيناريو تعزيز الطاقة المتجددة الثانى RE2 بين العامين ٢٠٢٢ و ٢٠٣٠؛ بينما تصل إلى ادنى مستوياتها فى السيناريو RE2 فى عام ٢٠٥٠. من المتوقع أيضا أن يسهم الغاز الطبيعى بالنصيب الأكبر فى إنتاج الطاقة فى السيناريو المرجعى الاول RS1 بينما يشارك بالنسبة الأقل فى السيناريو RE2 بحلول عام ٢٠٥٠ حيث تسيطر طاقة الرياح على إنتاج الطاقة. اظهرت النتائج ان من بين جميع السيناريوهات التى تم اختبارها يتمتع سيناريو تعزيز الطاقة المتجددة الثانى RE2 بالإحتمالية الأكبر فى تحقيق الانبعاثات الصفرية على المدى البعيد.

الكلمات الدالة: تغيير المناخ ، مصر، النماذج الاحتمالية، LEAP

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الاجازة

أجازت لجنة المناقشة هذه الرسالة للحصول على درجة الدكتوراة في الدراسات الأوروبية المتوسطة بتقدير/ امتياز بتاريخ 2025/4/6 بعد استيفاء جميع المتطلبات.

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برنامج الدراسات الأوروبية المتوسطة

سيناريوهات التخطيط البديل لتقليل الانبعاثات الدفئية من قطاع الطاقة: تطبيق نموذج LEAP على قطاع الطاقة فى مصر

اعداد

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رسالة مقدمة الى قسم الاقتصاد

كجزء من متطلبات الحصول علي درجة الدكتوراة فى الدراسات الأوروبية المتوسطة

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